

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF INTERNATIONAL HEALTH

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**WORK STRESS AND RESILIENCE AMONG NURSES WORKING IN EXTENDED
HOURS DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC AT TERTIARY HOSPITALS IN METRO
MANILA, PHILIPPINES**

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11 October 2023

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Acceptance Page

This Thesis titled: “**Work Stress and Resilience Among Nurses Working in Extended Hours During COVID-19 Pandemic at Tertiary Hospitals in Metro Manila Philippines**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, University of the Philippines Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of International Health Program.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my advisor, Professor Queenie Roxas-Ridulme, MAN, RN, for their guidance, support, and encouragement throughout this project. Their insights and expertise have been invaluable to me, and I am truly grateful for their mentorship.

I would also like to thank my critic, Dr. Evelyn Victoria Reside, FPCP, FPCCP, MAS, the members of my thesis panel, Dr. Myra Oruga, MPH, Dr. Josephine Agapito, and Professor Ma. Elma Mirandilla, MAN, RN, for their thoughtful feedback and suggestions. Their comments have helped me to improve my thesis immeasurably.

I am also grateful to Jose Reyes R. Memorial Medical Center, Amang Rodrigues Memorial Medical Center, and The Medical City for providing me with the opportunity to conduct my research. Their support has been essential to the completion of this project.

I am also thankful to my statistician, Kevynn P. Delgado, MBA, MS, for his invaluable contribution to the statistical analysis of my study. To my sister, Rae Belle Charisse Sandoval, for giving her time to proofread and check the grammar of my thesis.

Finally, I would like to thank my friends and family for their love and support. Their encouragement has helped me to stay motivated throughout this process.

This thesis would not have been possible without the help and support of all of these individuals. I am truly grateful for their contributions.

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 pandemic is a global health crisis that has a significant impact on the health of nurses in the Philippines. This study aims to determine the correlation between work stress and resilience of nurses who worked extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at a tertiary hospital in Metro Manila. A descriptive-correlation design was utilized as the research design in this study involving nurses. The study included 128 nurse respondents aged 21-59, who experienced working more than 8-hour shifts, and those who rendered direct care to patients with COVID-19 both adult and pediatrics. The survey was conducted from February 1, 2021, to January 31, 2022, at three tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila both private and public. The level of work stress was measured using the Nurses' Occupational Stressor Scale (NOSS) and work resilience with the Resilience Scale for Nurses (RSN). The NOSS was found to be the most significant predictor of work stress among nurses working in prolonged working hours. This research generated data designed to show that work stress has a negative relationship, using Pearson Correlation and Spearman Rank Correlation, and statistical significance with work resilience among nurses who worked extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, negative relationship and statistical significance, using Pearson Correlation, were also found in the following demographics: (1) Three years or less at current hospital, (2) married, (3) assigned to COVID-19 ward, COVID-19 pedia, COVID-19 ICU, and COVID-19 OR.

Chapter 1

THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

Background of the Study

Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, nurses in the Philippines already experienced burnout and dissatisfaction with their operating conditions thus leading to job dissatisfaction and emotional exhaustion (Rosales et al., 2013). This was also personally experienced by the researcher when he worked at the emergency department of a tertiary private hospital in 2018 as he experienced being recalled to work to render extra duty or usually required to render a 12-hour duty two to three times a week because of the depleted workforce. Nurses also do not have the option to take a leave with pay until their first year at work. This claim is supported by a report in *The Japan Times*, 2021, that nurses in the Philippines are forced to work long hours or up to 15 hours per shift in severe COVID-19 cases to compensate for the short staffing both at private and public hospitals responding to the pandemic. The country battled with the surge of delta variant in the third quarter of 2021 thus leading to the exhaustion of the nurses. Despite being the world's biggest exporter of healthcare workers, the country is short of nurses, (*The Japan Times*, 2021).

In January 2022, the researcher was augmented as a staff nurse at the emergency department of another private tertiary hospital for a month during the surge of the Omicron variant of COVID-19. The regular staff nurses in the same hospital still experience extended working hours due to reduced manpower afflicted by the disease and some were already complaining among the nurses that they don't want to work overtime anymore. It is also visually evident that a lot of the staff were new and

probationary as more nurses from the unit were flying abroad. This is supported by the study of Labrague et al., 2020, that nurses in the Philippines have high turnover intention compared with other international studies, the Philippines has about 50% of nurses want to leave their institution within one year of employment and more than 75% are planning to leave within five years. Several main causes were listed by Labrague et al., 2020, as to why nurses in the Philippines intend to leave their work and these are the following: (1) psychological stress, (2) job burnout, and (3) job dissatisfaction.

According to the World Health Organization South-East Asia Regional Office, 2020, the countries in South-East Asia need 1.9 million more nurses and midwives to achieve health for all by 2030. In 2018, the region had only 3.5 million nurses and midwives, or 18 per 10,000 population, far from the global average of 37 nurses and midwives per 10,000 population and a required minimum of 40 nurses in every 10,000 population (World Health Organization South-East Asia Regional Office, 2020). Every country must maintain the recommended number of nurses and midwives for health security, especially during this global outbreak of COVID-19 (World Health Organization South-East Asia Regional Office, 2020).

Wong, Chan, and Ngan, (2019) stated in their study that many researchers concluded that there is an association between depression and long working hours. Working more than 34-48 hours per week increases the risk of anxiety and depression. Furthermore, an increase in working hours contributed to psychological stress, work stress, and sleep deprivation yields fatigue, and risk of occupational injury (Wong, Chan, & Ngan, 2019). Park, et al., 2020, also stated in their study the same impacts on mental secondary to longer working hours in a survey conducted among Koreans.

It was revealed that as the working hours increase, the risk for stress, depression, and suicide ideation also increases, (Park et al., 2020).

In an article published by Biana & Joaquin, 2020, there is a need to address the psychological, emotional, and spiritual well-being of the general population, but there is also a need for these interventions among healthcare workers battling the pandemic. Health workers in the Philippines are already experiencing shift fatigue even before the pandemic and the surge has increased the problem drastically, (Biana & Joaquin, 2020). To address these issues, further studies on the effects of extended working hours among healthcare workers responding to the pandemic in the Philippines are needed.

Alfonso, Fonseca, & Pires, 2017, evaluated the relationship between a longer working hours group (LWHG) and a regular working hours group (RWHG) in the sleep quality, anxiety, and depression symptoms using the hospital anxiety and depression scale (HADS). It showed that the LWHG had significantly more depressive and anxiety symptoms, and worse sleep quality compared to RWHG, (Alfonso, Fonseca, & Pires, 2017).

This study aims to find the correlation between work stress and resilience of nurses working extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at a tertiary hospital in Metro Manila. The result of this study would be used to recommend the appropriate working hours and other interventions to maintain the quality of psychological well-being of our healthcare workers with or without the pandemic and render optimal health care to their clients.

Statement of the Problem

Since the beginning of the pandemic, healthcare workers have been forced to extend their working hours, more than 8 hours per shift, to compensate for the understaffed health facilities, increased admission of COVID-19 patients, and staff getting infected with COVID-19 in the country.

Is there a significant relationship between work stress and the resilience of nurses working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila?

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine the relationship between work stress and resilience among nurses working extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila, Philippines.

The study specifically seeks to answer the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of work stress of nurses working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals according to the Nurses' Occupational Stressor Scale (NOSS):
 - 1.1 Work demands
 - 1.2 Work-family conflict
 - 1.3 Insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers
 - 1.4 Workplace violence and bullying
 - 1.5 Organizational issues
 - 1.6 Occupational hazards
 - 1.7 Difficulty taking leave

1.8 Powerlessness

1.9 Unmet physiological needs

2. To describe the level of work resilience of the nurses working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals according to the Resilience Scale for Nurses (RSN):

2.1 Philosophical pattern

2.2 Relational pattern

2.3 Situational pattern

2.4 Dispositional pattern

3. To determine the relationship between work stress and resilience of nurses working in extended working hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila, Philippines.

4. To determine the work stress of nurses who work extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic in their demographic profile.

5. To determine the work resilience of nurses who work extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic in their demographic profile.

The study also aims to use the information from the data collected to be used by the hospital and nursing administrators in decision-making for implementing interventions for the mental well-being of nurses and improving the work environment, especially during pandemics or surges of emerging and re-emerging infectious diseases. This will also help hospital administrators how to treat our nurses better.

Significance of Study

This study will be specifically beneficial to nurses at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila, the Philippines in improving their work environment and thus improving their

mental health status, especially during a public health emergency or a pandemic. Mental health wellness among nurses is beneficial to nursing administration and clients as the workforce for healthcare services will not be depleted and quality care will not be compromised. Hospital administrators and human resources (HR) will also benefit from this study to improve the environment and develop management strategies not just for nurses but also for other healthcare professionals including physicians, medical technologists, pharmacists, etc., and improve stress management among healthcare professionals, especially during a pandemic.

A well-functioning healthcare system is beneficial to the economy as more sick people can get immediate quality care, thus equating themselves to a better prognosis and preventing the loss of lives and further loss of income due to prolonged morbidity.

Scope and Limitation

The study focused on concepts of NOSS and its nine (9) subcategories: (1) work demands, (2) work-family conflict, (3) insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers, (4) workplace violence and bullying, (5) organizational issues, (6) occupational hazards, (7) difficulty taking leave, (8) powerlessness, and (9) unmet physiological needs. As well as the four (4) subscales of RSN which include: (1) philosophical pattern, (2) relational pattern, (3) situational pattern, and (4) dispositional pattern.

This study included 128 nurse respondents aged 21-59, who experienced working more than 8-hour-shift and those who rendered direct care to COVID-19 patients in emergency rooms both adult and pediatrics, COVID wards, operating rooms, and intensive care units (ICU) from February 1, 2021 to January 31, 2022.

Non-probability sampling was used in the research due to its practical, faster, and more cost-effective method for the researcher. This method also highlighted the relationship between the work stress of nurses and their resilience based on their sociodemographics. It significantly answered the question if work stress and resilience among nurses differ based on their sociodemographics.

The scope of the study is limited to nurses who are working at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila, Philippines during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study is also limited to the use of NOSS and RSN tools which are not yet validated for use among Filipino nurses as no other study used both tools for correlation. Getting a larger sample size was also limited as other tertiary hospitals declined to participate in the survey due to various reasons and several nurses who worked during the pandemic are no longer working at the three hospitals mentioned above or even in the Philippines.

Chapter 2

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Review of Related Literature

In the GMA News Online report (2022), the Philippine Nurses Association (PNA) reported on June 6, 2022, that over 300,000 licensed nurses in the Philippines are currently working overseas. According to Lei Alviz's report on "24 Oras," the most recent Department of Health (DOH) data show that over 316,000 of the country's 617,898 registered and practicing nurses are employed abroad as of December 2021. According to the Philippine Overseas Employment Administration (POEA), these estimates climbed in January 2022 when at least 2,000 more healthcare personnel decided to migrate overseas (GMA News Online, 2022). According to the Private Hospitals Association of the Philippines Inc. (PHAPI), these numbers indicate that the capacity of hospitals is increasing, particularly when the number of patients increases (GMA News Online, 2022).

In a study conducted by Davey et al., 2014, they found that Indian staff nurses usually experience moderate stress due to posting in busy departments, insufficient pay, being overworked, time pressure, poor physician's attitude, and exhausting work without enough rest and meals.

COVID-19 did not only affect the healthcare workers in the Philippines but all over the world. Clinicians in Greece have faced increasing difficulties that they have never encountered throughout the COVID-19 pandemic. With limited resources, quick decisions must be taken on everything from effectively triaging and isolating patients with infection suspicions to deciding whether to close departments and operating

rooms when a patient or member of the staff tests positive. It has been extremely difficult to diagnose, isolate, and treat patients effectively and promptly, especially in the face of heavy public and media attention. This is consistent with what has been observed in other nations. In addition, our frontline doctors, nurses, and healthcare professionals worry that they might get COVID-19 themselves due to the increased risk of exposure to the virus. Because of this, and similar to the situation during the SARS and H1N1 epidemics, healthcare practitioners managing COVID-19 are under significant psychological stress and incur high rates of psychiatric morbidity. Anxiety and stress disorders are common among front-line medical staff, with nurses reporting greater rates of anxiety than doctors, according to a fairly recent study among healthcare professionals in a tertiary infectious disease hospital in China for COVID-19. Although anecdotal, the experience at our hospitals over the previous few weeks is consistent with these reports. Healthcare personnel have experienced "overflowing" anxiety and despair as a result of the disruption of ordinary clinical practice, a sense of loss of control, and the accompanying dread of a possible instability of the health services, a characteristic that is common to epidemics. Older healthcare professionals with concurrent medical disorders may have higher morbidity due to depression, which is linked to poor medication adherence. (Tsamakis et al., 2020)

In 2020, healthcare systems across the world were presented with unprecedented challenges in responding to COVID-19 (Arnetz, Goetz, Arnetz, & Arble, 2020). According to United Nations', 2020, Policy Brief: The Impact of COVID-19 on South-East Asia, the Philippines is lagging behind its South-East Asian neighbors in terms of nurses and midwives ratio to its people, from 2010 to 2018, with only 2 in every 100,000. This is followed by Cambodia, Myanmar, and Laos with 10, Timor-Leste with 17, Vietnam with 14, Indonesia with 21, Thailand with 30, Malaysia with 41,

Brunei with 66, and Singapore with most in the region with 72 nurses and midwives per 100,000 people. Nurses are one of the receivers of this great impact that is damaging to their occupational health and safety as well as to their mental health (Arnetz, Goetz, Arnetz, & Arble, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic has added to their work stress and was already strained before the pandemic began (Arnetz, Goetz, Arnetz, & Arble, 2020). Nurses who had direct care of COVID-19 patients were more at risk for mental health issues according to studies from China and Italy, countries that experienced the early onslaught of the pandemic (Arnetz, Goetz, Arnetz, & Arble, 2020).

Nurses in Pakistan continue to experience the damaging effects of the COVID-19 pandemic, in 2021, on their mental health which includes depression, anxiety, and stress (Nadeem et al., 2021). Thus, there was a need to assess the burden on mental health and develop interventions for the nurses to function properly and provide the utmost care for their patients (Nadeem et al., 2021).

Work Stress Among Healthcare Workers Including Nurses in South-East Asian Region During COVID-19 Pandemic

In a study conducted by Tunthanathip et al., 2021, stress, among healthcare workers in Southern Thailand, has been high during the COVID-19 pandemic causing a risk factor for burnout. There were 18.4% of the total participants who were in the risk group of stress during the COVID-19 outbreak which was reduced to 10.8% after the lockdown period (Tunthanathip et al., 2021). It was recommended to highly supervise healthcare workers with high risk to prevent physical and mental illness in the future (Tunthanathip et al., 2021).

Work stress and burnout among healthcare workers in Singapore were mild over the six months of the pandemic in the country (Teo et al., 2021). However, anxiety varied by pandemic-response occurrence (Teo et al., 2021). Teo et al., 2021, suggested interventions to lessen the stress among healthcare workers in Singapore such as promoting teamwork and appreciating them at work.

According to Al Sabei et al., 2022, the availability of high levels of job resources reduces job-related burnout, whereas high levels of job demands can cause job burnout, according to the job-resources demand model (Taris & Schaufeli, 2016). Job resources are elements of the job that are essential to achieving organizational goals, lowering workload demands, and promoting personal development and growth (Zhou et al., 2022). Due to the rising number of infected individuals, including healthcare personnel, Oman had a shortage of both material and human resources during the COVID-19 epidemic. The literature emphasized the value of work environment and structural empowerment as organizational coping mechanisms during earlier pandemics like the swine flu pandemic (H1N1), the severe acute respiratory syndrome, and the Middle East, breathing disorder (Barello et al., 2020). Limited data, however, evaluated how the COVID-19 situation's work environment and structural empowerment affected stress levels. The components of the work environment and structural empowerment were therefore viewed as job resources in the current study, while psychological stress was seen as a reflection of perceived job demand.

Nurses in Malaysia also showed moderate and high levels of stress due to the COVID-19 pandemic in a cross-sectional national online survey conducted by Chui et al., 2021. Out-patient department nurses showed higher levels of stress compared to nurses in inpatient care departments due to the uncertainty of cases of patients they encounter all the time (Chui et al., 2021). It was recommended to provide nurses with

appropriate mental health and coping strategies regularly even after the pandemic (Chui et al., 2021).

As burnout and compassion fatigue are tightly related, the concept of secondary trauma is more explicitly defined as the second exposure to those who have gone through significantly or traumatically stressful circumstances. As was to be expected, healthcare workers who treated COVID-19 patients displayed higher levels of secondary trauma than their peers, although this result differs from those of Li et al., who found that non-frontline nurses had higher levels of this variable than frontline nurses. The authors speculate that the increased psychological endurance of frontline nurses may help to explain their data. This suggests that frontline medical staff may be more habituated to potentially upsetting experiences than non-frontline staff, resulting in a less negative reaction to trying circumstances. In contrast, the frontline group, which was compared to non-frontline colleagues, revealed greater levels of secondary trauma (Trumello et al., 2020)

Vietnam has been quite successful in controlling COVID-19 in 2020, Nguyen et al., 2021, surveyed healthcare workers, which includes physicians, nurses, and laboratory workers, from Da Nang City regarding their working conditions and factors associated with stress during the COVID-19 pandemic. The result of their study showed that 46.3% of nurses surveyed experienced stress due to overwork, direct contact with critical COVID-19 patients, and fear of contracting an infection and passing it to their relatives (Nguyen et al., 2021). It was recommended to reduce working time, secure enough PPE provisions, and increase the knowledge of healthcare workers in responding to COVID-19 to reduce their stress and increase their efficiency as healthcare workers (Nguyen et al., 2021).

Myanmar's healthcare system has been facing challenges ever since and includes one of the world's lowest health workforces with only 10 nurses and midwives in every 10,000 population in 2018 (Oo, Tun, Lin, and Lucero-Prisno, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic added to the burden experienced by the healthcare workers in Myanmar thus exhausting them because of a heavy workload, insufficient supply of personal protective equipment (PPEs), and fear of spreading the infection (Oo, Tun, Lin, and Lucero-Prisno, 2020). Conflicts and civil wars in Myanmar greatly affect and pose challenges in addressing the pandemic in the country (Oo, Tun, Lin, and Lucero-Prisno, 2020).

Meanwhile, nurses in the Philippines both in community and clinical settings experienced the same level of fear of COVID-19, with more occurrences with female nurses than males, thus increasing the level of work stress and professional turnover intentions (De los Santos & Labrague, 2021). It was recommended by De los Santos & Labrague, 2021, to institute psychological support services, and stress reduction activities to provide nurses with assurance, comfort, and mental health wellness. It is also to be noted that the provision of enough personal protective equipment for nurses exposed to COVID-19 patients can reduce their feelings of fear and anxiety about contracting the disease as well (De los Santos & Labrague, 2021).

Work Stress

Chen et al., 2020, developed a NOSS tool to evaluate the stressors of nurses in Asia working at hospitals. The NOSS has nine subscales which include: (1) work demands, (2) work-family conflict, (3) insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers, (4) workplace violence, and bullying, (5) organizational issues, (6) occupational hazards, (7) difficulty taking leave, (8) powerlessness, and (9) unmet

basic physiological needs (Chen et al., 2020). It is very important that before we proceed with stress management, we identify the stressors that may be eliminated through a validated assessment scale (Chen et al., 2020).

Work Demands

A study has shown that work demands can yield stress to nurses and eventually affect their job performance (Al-Homayan et al., 2013). Job demand was described as a level at which a working environment includes provocations that need some effort (Al-Homayan et al., 2013). Job demands can be challenging as a stressor and can promote growth and productivity among employees; on the other hand, they can also be unpleasant, undesirable, and excessive, which can be a hindrance to productivity (Al-Homayan et al., 2013).

Work-Family Conflict

Sharma et al., 2016, mentioned that work and family are both indispensable parts of the lives of nurses and must be able to reconcile their roles to function properly. Work-family conflict can also cause stress among nurses and its successive impact on their mental health (Sharma et al., 2016). Furthermore, it was found that work-family conflict has a direct negative relationship with the mental health of female nurses (Sharma et al., 2016).

The frontliners during the pandemic were more prone to anxiety and stress due to their fear of infection for themselves and their families. Increased physical demands on patients cause significant burnout in the form of emotional tiredness, depersonalization, and diminished self-achievement. In the current study, emergency department frontline nurses reported moderate to high levels of emotional exhaustion

(29.13 10.30) and depersonalization (12.90 4.67) burnout, while burnout was less pronounced in the domain of personal accomplishment (37.68 5.17) (Jose et al.,2020).

Insufficient Support from Coworkers or Caregivers

Nurses must receive support extrinsically to achieve the standard goal in the institution (Sodeify, Vanaki, & Mohammadi, 2013). The role of encouragement and support among nurses improves their performance at work and care for their clients (Sodeify, Vanaki, & Mohammadi, 2013). Furthermore, when nurses have autonomy and are empowered, hospitals cultivate a culture of cooperation and trust (Sodeify, Vanaki, & Mohammadi, 2013). On the other hand, Sodeify, Vanaki, & Mohammadi, 2013, stated that a poor organizational climate hurts the performance of the nurses.

Furthermore, prolonged workplace stress can harm a nurse's ability to fulfill their duties. A study (Park & Jung, 2021) findings showed that when participants' COVID-19 nursing preparedness levels were high, their levels of job stress were noticeably reduced. Organizational culture and environmental factors have been demonstrated to have an impact on nurses' levels of occupational stress. The new study backs up a prior study that contends that sufficient organizational assistance is required during the pandemic.

Workplace Violence and Bullying

In a study conducted by Zhang et al., 2018, they concluded that the majority 75.4% of Chinese nurses who participated in their study experienced a significant negative influence on work stress due to workplace violence (WPV). Homayuni, Hosseini, Aghamolaei, & Shahini, 2021, discussed in their research that bullying among nurses is a recognized problem universally that yields issues for nurses,

clients, and the institutions to which they belong. It was also found in the study of Homayuni, Hosseini, Aghamolaei, & Shahini, 2021, that the victim's character affects the enactment of bullying; however, this does not justify blaming the victim of bullying. Zhang et al., 2018, recommended a need for a harmonious work environment for nurses for the damage to health outcomes caused by WPV. Homayuni, Hosseini, Aghamolaei, & Shahini, 2021, strengthen this recommendation and institutions should implement anti-bullying policies to support staff.

Organizational Issues

One of the organizational issues discussed by Labrague et al., 2016, is organizational politics (OP) in healthcare settings may yield competing interests, power plays, and conflict between or among nurse employees. Labrague et al., 2016, concluded that OP perceptions have negative impacts on job satisfaction and increase stress and burnout levels among nurses. In addition to that, it was also cited in the research of Fallahi-Khoshknab, Ghavidel, Molavynejad, & Zarea, 2019, that ineffective administrative approaches in the institution together with insufficient supply of equipment and human resources can lead to emotional exhaustion, stress, poorer service quality, high employee turnover, and early retirement of psychiatric nurses in Iran. Thus, there is a need to identify both the negative and positive factors affecting the quality of care of nurses to improve healthcare services to patients (Fallahi-Khoshknab, Ghavidel, Molavynejad, & Zarea, 2019).

Occupational Hazards

Health workers, including nurses, in Turkey, and throughout the world experience various hazards and risks at their workplace while providing their services

(Ulutaşdemir, Balsak, Berhuni, Özdemir, & Ataşalan, 2015). It was also noted in the study of Hu, Luk, & Smith, 2015, that workplace hazard significantly contributes to the occurrence of stress or emotional exhaustion and depersonalization in nurses in Macau. It was concluded in the study of Ulutaşdemir, Balsak, Berhuni, Özdemir, & Ataşalan, 2015, that health workers experience work stress and deteriorated health due to occupational hazards; and thus, yield inferior quality health care services among their clients. It was recommended that there is a need to identify the sources of workplace hazards to create appropriate interventions (Hu, Luk, & Smith, 2015).

Difficulty Taking Leave

The study by Chen et al., 2020, including the difficulty of taking leave for family-related reasons among Japanese nurses adds to their burnout or worse death due to overwork. Japanese nurses feel guilty about taking leave without replacement because other nurses would be forced to compensate by working more hours (Chen et al., 2020). Alnazly, Khraisat, Al-Bashaireh, & Bryant, 2021 mentioned in their study that taking vacation leaves among healthcare workers, including nurses, lessen the levels of fear, depression, anxiety, and stress. Furthermore, was also highlighted that during pandemic situations, vacation leave from work helps in lessening psychological distress and thus leads to lower levels of depression, fear, anxiety, and stress among healthcare workers (Alnazly, Khraisat, Al-Bashaireh, & Bryant, 2021).

Powerlessness

The feeling of powerlessness has been reported among nurses that contributed to their moral dilemmas and burnout (Kornhaber & Wilson, 2011). It was also mentioned in the study of Kornhaber & Wilson, 2011, that powerlessness among

nurses revolves around issues of pain management, treatment options, and death of patients that result in feelings of inadequacy, apprehension, vulnerability, and frustration.

Davey et al., 2014, showed in their study that Indian nurses were about 3 to 4 times more likely to experience professional stress due to poor and satisfactory doctor's attitudes towards them than to doctors with excellent attitudes. In the same study, only 5% of nurses revealed poor doctors' attitudes toward them versus 21% of the nurses perceived poor attitudes from the patients. However, poor doctors' attitude toward nurses significantly associates them with professional stress (Davey et al., 2014).

Unmet Basic Physiological Needs

Cappelletti, Kreuter, Boyum, & Thompson, 2015, stated in their study that basic physiological needs such as food, shelter, safety, and money can go unmet in economically disadvantaged populations and may yield adverse physical and mental health outcomes. As unmet basic needs increased, the perceived stress of the respondents, in the study by Cappelletti, Kreuter, Boyum, & Thompson, 2015, also increased. Furthermore, in the study by Davey, Sharma, Davey, & Shukla, 2019, they found that inadequate salary is one of the most important factors responsible for high-level stress among nurses. It is noteworthy that assessing stress and job satisfaction among nurses should be done continuously for monitoring and reevaluation to create a better working environment and lessen their burden on the job (Davey, Sharma, Davey, & Shukla, 2019).

Based on Article 83 of the Department of Labor and Employment Guidelines (: The normal hours of work of any employee shall not exceed eight (8) hours a day. Thus, making those who work more than eight hours a day, more susceptible and vulnerable to exhaustion and anxiety. It is also stated that health personnel in cities and municipalities with a population of at least one million (1,000,000) or in hospitals and clinics with a bed capacity of at least one hundred (100) shall hold regular office hours for eight (8) hours a day, for five (5) days a week, exclusive of time for meals, except where the exigencies of the service require that such personnel work for six (6) days or forty-eight (48) hours, in which case, they shall be entitled to additional compensation of at least thirty percent (30%) of their regular wage for work on the sixth day. For purposes of this Article, "health personnel" shall include resident physicians, nurses, nutritionists, dietitians, pharmacists, social workers, laboratory technicians, paramedical technicians, psychologists, midwives, attendants, and all other hospital or clinic personnel.

In Article 84, the work hours per se are explained as: Hours worked shall include (a) all time during which an employee is required to be on duty or to be at a prescribed workplace; and (b) all time during which an employee is suffered or permitted to work. Rest periods of short duration during working hours shall be counted as hours worked.

Work Resilience Among Healthcare Workers Including Nurses in South-East Asian Region During COVID-19 Pandemic

A study conducted by Setiawati et al., 2021, in Indonesia showed a significant correlation between the level of work resilience and anxiety of healthcare workers, where 59% of the respondents are nurses. As the level of work resilience decreases,

the level of anxiety of healthcare workers also increases (Setiawati et al., 2021). The study recommends institutions create policies to help healthcare workers including nurses to increase their level of work resilience and avoid mental health issues (Setiawati et al., 2021).

A cross-sectional multi-country study revealed how healthcare workers cope with mental health challenges during COVID-19 which includes nurses from Myanmar, Philippines, and Thailand (Htay et al., 2021). The study concluded that healthcare workers preferred family support, positive thinking, and religious/prayers as strategies for coping with the psychological impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic (Htay et al., 2021). Htay et al., 2021, recommended getting family support, social support, and participation in mindfulness practices to improve the work resilience of healthcare workers at a personal level during the COVID-19 pandemic. Furthermore, institutions are recommended to create a positive workplace and teamwork collaboration, promote adequate rest and sleep by arranging work schedules in favor of the healthcare workers, provide lounges at the workplace for healthcare workers to rest during long shifts, and importantly, provide psychosocial support and counseling to improve work resilience of the healthcare workers (Htay et al., 2021).

Work Resilience of Nurses

An international view of nurses' work resilience in the face of COVID-19 study by Jo et al., 2021, showed that respondents had a mean work resilience of 26.5 and a standard deviation (SD) of ± 7.0 which is an intermediate level. Concerning intention to leave, the nurses had a mean score of 3.1 or SD of ± 3.6 ; therefore, concluded that work resilience is inversely associated with the intention of nurses to leave (Jo et al.,

2021). As the work resilience of nurses increases, the intention of nurses to leave decreases (Jo et al., 2021).

According to Lorente et al., 2020, states that the study made by Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) transactional model of stress and coping, coping is a process that involves both cognitive and behavioral reactions people employ to try to handle internal and/or external pressures that they believe to be beyond their resources. The various coping strategies can be divided into two categories: palliative or emotion-focused coping (EFC) and direct action or problem-focused coping (PFC). According to Lazarus (2000), these two coping mechanisms complement one another and are interdependent, with coping serving as a crucial process that mediates the relationship between an individual and their environment (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). PFC describes a person's endeavor to neutralize a perceived danger. Making things better, entails decreasing the sources of stress at work. EFC then seeks to lessen any emotional distress or other adverse impacts brought on by the circumstance. According to earlier studies (Grossi, 1999; Wong et al., 2006), PFC is positively related to well-being indicators, reducing anxiety and psychological distress, whereas EFC shows more erratic results regarding its relationship with well-being (Day & Livingstone, 2003; González-Morales et al., 2010). No matter what, coping mechanisms, such as "fight" or "flight," are meant to shield individuals from the damaging consequences of stressors on their psychological and physical well-being (Lepore & Evans, 1996). In one situation, protection results by eliminating the stressful causes, while in the other, it results from avoidance or other cognitive or emotional techniques. However, Mayordomo-Rodríguez et al. (2015) discovered that the relationship between EFC and well-being is not always good. It is crucial to understand how these two coping mechanisms could potentially moderate the association

between stressors and nurses' mental health. Previous studies have provided evidence that coping has a partial mediating role in the association between stress and health (Klainin-Yobas et al., 2014) and in the relationship between psychological capital and psychological distress in Chinese nurses (Zhou et al., 2017). On some occasions, it has been demonstrated that the mediation effect differs for the two ways of coping.

Additionally, according to Chowdhury et al., 2021, the healthcare personnel in Bangladesh are stressed and concerned due to foreseeable stock shortages and an increase in reported and actual COVID-19 reports.

Males in the study they conducted showed lower levels of despair, anxiety, and stress as well as psychological effects during the COVID-19 outbreak than did females. This result was consistent with earlier research showing that during the COVID-19 pandemic, women experienced more mental anguish and had worse mental health outcomes. Their research revealed that nurses with lesser educational backgrounds had less psychological impact from the COVID-19 pandemic and had lower sadness, anxiety, and stress scores, indicating less mental anguish than nurses with higher educational backgrounds. A UK study, however, found that working with patients was less stressful if the nurses had more training and knew how to handle mental health issues. This unexpected result may be because less educated nurses in Bangladeshi healthcare settings were given fewer responsibilities and leadership roles, which reduced their exposure to potentially stressful situations.

Similarly in the Philippines, work resilience among nurses is a protective factor against the effects of compassion fatigue, yields higher job satisfaction and increased

work retention, and a higher quality of care provided to patients (Labrague & de los Santos, 2021).

Park, Choi & Kim, 2019, validated a resilience scale for nurses to determine their holistic intrinsic capacity to adapt to a stressful environment. Furthermore, it also mentioned the importance of work resilience among nurses to progressively conquer several obstacles in clinical settings, show professional competencies, and consistently provide the utmost care for their patients (Park, Choi & Kim, 2019). The resilience model used by Park, Choi & Kim, 2019, in the study, has four factors which include: (1) philosophical pattern, (2) relational pattern, (3) situational pattern, and (4) dispositional pattern. The validated RSN tool is found to be reliable and can be used to identify actual clinical nurses' work resilience (Park, Choi & Kim, 2019).

In the study of Şenocak, Demirkıran, and Totan, 2021, they used the validated resilience scale for nurses by Park, Choi, & Kim, 2019 which aims to determine four factors of resilience based on Polk's (1997) model. The philosophical pattern measures the personal principles and optimistic outlooks of the nurse from the time to come (Şenocak, Demirkıran, and Totan, 2021). Next is the relational pattern which assesses the interpersonal relationship of the nurse (Şenocak, Demirkıran, and Totan, 2021). Then, the dispositional pattern determines self-confidence, self-efficiency, and self-reliance, which permits the nurses to be independent in solving their problems (Şenocak, Demirkıran, and Totan, 2021). Lastly, situational pattern measures an individual to adapt to stressful situations with consideration to patience (Şenocak, Demirkıran, and Totan, 2021).

According to research by Sul et al., 2015, resilience rises with age. Job banding revealed that average resilience scores were moderate, indicating that people at this

level may already have some resilience-related traits but that they still need to be developed. Similar results were observed for resilience by Ang et al., who also found that age and employment experience were related to increased resilience. Similar findings were made when Purvis et al. looked at resilience and burnout in staff members of neurological critical care units. In Ang's study, having a higher degree also affected resilience, although our survey design did not look at this.

Philosophical Pattern

Koen, van Eeden, Wisconsin & du Plessis, 2011, mentioned in their study that philosophies including the beliefs of the nurses promote or enable their work resilience from an ecological perspective in viewing their interpersonal relationships. The philosophies of the nurses give essence to their work resilience capabilities in their profession (Koen, van Eeden, Wissin & du Plessis, 2011).

Relational Pattern

Hudgins, 2015, mentioned in her study that nurse leaders can develop work resilience and enhance the relational pattern of work resilience through a professional and personal network of optimistic mentors and cheerleaders. Furthermore, nurse leaders can empower others to reduce workload and develop new leaders in the unit (Hudgins, 2015).

Dispositional Pattern

Positive disposition of staff such as nurses provides benefits for the organizations and the help, they provide to people and families who are dealing with adverse situations (Jackson, Firtko & Edenborough, 2007). Work resilience among

nursing staff promotes retention and prevents abandoning their career path when challenges in the healthcare system become overwhelming (Jackson, Firtko & Edenborough, 2007).

Situational Pattern

Situations like violence among emergency room nurses in South Korea affect their work resilience, coping, competency, and burnout in a study by Lee & Sung, 2017. A coping program was initiated that improved work resilience and provided a positive effect on coping with violence and competency among emergency room nurses (Lee & Sung, 2017).

Relationship between Work Stress and Resilience

Badu et al., 2020, discussed in their study the workplace stress and resilience among nurses in Australia and indicated that they experience moderate to high levels of stress that are largely associated with workplace bullying. It was concluded in the same study that there are several interventions among organizations the nurses to help in work resilience and manage work adversity (Badu et al., 2020). Work resilience interventions are feasible and positively accepted to improve the mental health of nurses in the workplace (Badu et al., 2020).

Shirali et al., 2021 also concluded in their study that the work stress of Iranian nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic has a strong and negative correlation with their work resilience and it was important to note the need for the provision of effective preventive and treatment modalities.

Synthesis

The study to be conducted aims to focus on the plight of nurses in the Philippine setting, specifically in the national capital region. The study also seeks to determine the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the work stress and resilience of nurses in the country knowing that they are already underappreciated, overworked, and underpaid even before the pandemic. There is little to no study that determines the impact of the pandemic and extended working hours on the work stress and resilience of nurses in Metro Manila, Philippines.

Theoretical Framework

Figure 1. Nurses' Occupational Stressors

The diagram shown above is the theoretical framework of **Nurses' Occupational Stress (NOSS)** developed by Chen et al., 2020 to predict the level of stress levels of nurses. The level of stress was assessed based on the nurses' working trait curves to compare existing methods for determining stress outcomes, this includes personal burnout, client-related burnout, job dissatisfaction, and intention to leave. (Chen et al., 2020).

Conceptual Framework

Figure 2. Relationship Between Work Stress and Resilience of Nurses

The diagram shows the conceptual framework of the study. Utilization of the framework, the research aims to determine the correlation between work stress and its nine subscales: (1) work demands, (2) work-family conflict, (3) insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers, (4) workplace violence and bullying, (5) organizational issues, (6) occupational hazards, (7) difficulty taking leave, (8) powerlessness, and (9) unmet basic physiological needs to the resilience of nurses and its four subscales: (1) philosophical pattern, (2) relational pattern, (3) situational pattern, and (4) dispositional

pattern – working on extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila, Philippines.

This study was guided by the use of both NOSS by Chen et al., 2020 and its relationship to RSN validated by Park, Choi, & Kim, 2019.

Operational Definition of Terms

Difficulty taking leave - Taking time off from work is not permitted despite the urgency or importance due to personal reasons.

Dispositional pattern - Determines self-confidence, self-efficiency, and self-reliance, that permits the nurses to be independent in solving their problems.

Extended working hours - Have worked more than 8 hours in a shift.

Insufficient support - When a nurse does not receive enough support and encouragement from coworkers to help them improve their performance at work and care for their clients.

Nurse - Bedside nurse working in private tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila, Philippines with more than 8 hours per shift during the pandemic.

Occupational hazards - Immediate physical and emotional threats to nurses are experienced in their workplace, specifically at the hospitals. This includes biohazards, injury, verbal abuse, threats, emotional abuse, etc.

Organizational issues - Problems that span several departments or units in an institution and affect the staff of the organization.

Philosophical pattern - Measures the personal principle and optimistic outlooks of the nurse from the time to come.

Powerlessness - Lack of strength or power making one helpless and totally of no use at an organization.

Relational pattern - Assesses the interpersonal relationship of nurses with their patients, co-workers, supervisors, and their own families.

Situational pattern - Measures an individual to adapt to stressful situations with consideration to patience.

Unmet basic physiological needs - Basic needs that cannot be afforded like taking a break from work to eat, use the toilet, have a proper sleep, and have shelter and clothing with the current salary.

Work demands - A level of working environment that includes provocations that need some effort and can be challenging or unpleasant as stressors.

Work stress - Harmful physiological and psychological responses that happen when the required capacity, resources, or needs of the nurses are not met after working more than 8 hours.

Work-family conflict - When work demands and family needs are not reconciled with their roles to function properly.

Work resilience - The ability of nurses to bounce back or return to their equilibrium of calmness and peace after difficult moments at work even after working more than 8 hours.

Workplace violence and bullying - Physical and emotional disturbances that a nurse experiences extrinsically at their workplace that tend to diminish one's esteem to be a competent professional healthcare provider.

Hypothesis

There is a significant correlation between work stress and resilience among nurses working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila, Philippines.

Chapter 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a descriptive correlational design to examine the relationship between variables. Mean and standard deviation were used to determine the levels of work stress and resilience of nurses working direct care to patients with COVID-19 at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila. Mean, Anova, and Tukey-Kramer posthoc tests were used to determine the significance of the relationship of frequency of extended working hours to the nurses' work stress and resilience. The correlational analysis (Pearson and Spearman) was used to identify the relationship between the two mentioned variables, work stress, and resilience.

Sampling Technique

The study used purposive sampling of nurses who rendered direct care to COVID-19 cases specifically to the three tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila, Philippines, both private and public.

Setting

The study took place at three tertiary medical institutions in Metro Manila, the Philippines, both private and public, during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Tertiary hospitals were chosen in the study since both private and government hospitals comply with International Standards in Patient Care and Administration.

Population

According to the National Database of Selected Human Resources for Health (NDHRHIS), 13,763 nurses are practicing or working in Levels 1, 2, 3, and 4 hospitals in the National Capital Region (NCR) as of December 2022. Of them, 6,319 are known to work at private hospitals, while the remaining 7,444 work in public or government institutions (eFOI Philippines, 2023). Participants in the study are nurses who rendered direct care to COVID-19 patients between February 1, 2021 to January 31, 2022, and are still employed at their hospital at the time of the survey.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Adult male and/or female registered nurses range from 21 to 59 years old.
2. Those who have direct care with patients who are suspected, probable, or confirmed with COVID-19.
3. Has rendered more than 8 hours of duty per shift from February 1, 2021, to January 31, 2022.
4. Nurses who are in any of the following employment statuses: HRH, contractual, or permanent position.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Nurses who have known and are clinically diagnosed with mental health illness and psychiatric conditions during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Sample Size

This research generated data designed to study correlates of Nurses' Occupational Stressor Scale and correlates of the validated Resilience Scale for Nurses to its frequency of extended working hours in a regionally representative target

sample of 128 respondents (see appendix for sample size computation) with 95% confidence level, 8% margin of error and 30% response rate based on a total population of nurses in the Philippines. The target respondents in each hospital are based on the available tenured nurses who are still retained at the hospital after the pandemic. The study used non-random purposive sampling specific for nurses who worked directly with COVID-19 patients in their current hospital between February 1, 2021 to January 31, 2022. The sample may be biased towards those who have been retained to work and may not reflect the experiences of those who have left the hospital. This research cannot aim for a specific sample size in a hospital because it is difficult to collect data on how many nurses have been retained since the pandemic. The sensitive nature of these data will require that the data be released through a restricted-use contract.

Table 1

Summary of the Sample Size in each Hospital during the Implementation of the Study

HOSPITAL	SAMPLE SIZE
Hospital A	59
Hospital B	57
Hospital C	12
TOTAL	128

Data Collection

Research Instrument

The first part of the survey consisted of the demographics of the respondents followed by 21 questions related to work stress and 19 questions related to work resilience, both with a 5-point Likert scale response. The aim was to survey 128 nurses who had direct care of COVID-19 patients in a tertiary hospital in Metro Manila from February 1, 2021, to January 31, 2022. (See Appendix C and D for research instrument.)

Procedure

Figure 3. Flow Chart for Data Collection

The survey was conducted with the help of a representative of each hospital for the recruitment to the online survey dissemination to the following areas, namely the emergency department, COVID-19 pediatric area, COVID-19 adult ward, COVID-19 operating room, COVID-19 delivery room, COVID-19 intensive care unit, COVID-19 swabbing area, OB ward and other areas catering to COVID-19 patients. All participants answered through an online survey many of them answered by scanning the QR code using their phones to direct them to the URL, some typed in the URL to

direct them to the online survey, and others used the link sent to them through multimedia messaging platforms. Representatives in each hospital were oriented regarding the study, selection criteria, and how the survey was conducted on their nurses. Confidentiality of their responses was ensured without the worry that it might affect their employment status. No email addresses or identifiers were collected on the entire survey.

Participants had 10-15 minutes to fill out the self-administered survey anonymously. All surveys were fully accepted and validated, and 128 completed survey results were included in the analysis.

Nurses' Occupational Stress Scale Questionnaire

Work stress among nurses was measured using the 21-item questionnaire NOSS developed by Chen et al., 2020. For this study, nine subscales of NOSS were used namely: 1) work demands (3 items; Q3, Q5, Q11), 2) work-family conflict (3 items; Q10, Q20, Q21), 3) insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers (3 items; Q12, Q13, Q15), 4) workplace violence and bullying (1 item; Q16), 5) organizational issues (3 items; Q4, Q6, Q18), 6) occupational hazards (2 items; Q1, Q19), 7) difficulty taking leave (2 items; Q2, Q8), 8) powerlessness (2 items; Q9, Q17), 9) unmet basic physiological needs (2 items; Q7, Q14).

Table 2*Interpretation of Mean Scores for NOSS*

Mean Range	Interpretation
1.00 – 1.80	Very low-stress
1.81 – 2.60	Low in stress
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate in stress
3.41 – 4.20	High in stress
4.21 – 5.00	Very high in stress

Resilience Scale for Nurses Questionnaire

Collected data from the NOSS questionnaire were correlated to the 19-item validated RSN questionnaire developed by Park, Choi & Kim, 2019. This study used four subscales including 1) philosophical pattern (6 items; Q33, Q34, Q35, Q36, Q37, Q38), 2) relational pattern (4 items; Q24, Q25, Q26, Q27), 3) situational pattern (3 items; Q28, Q29, Q30), and 4) dispositional pattern (6 items; Q22, Q23, Q31, Q32, Q39, Q40). ANOVA will be used to determine if there is a significant difference in work stress as the frequency of extended working hours in a month increases. Tukey-Kramer post hoc test will be used if there is an observed significant difference in ANOVA.

Table 3*Interpretation of Mean Scores for RSN*

Mean Range	Interpretation
1.00 – 1.80	Very low in resilience
1.81 – 2.60	Low in resilience
2.61 – 3.40	Moderate in resilience
3.41 – 4.20	High in resilience
4.21 – 5.00	Very high resilience

Table 4

Plan for Data Analysis

Objectives	Variables	Level of Measurement	Statistical Test
1. To describe the level of work stress of nurses working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals according to NOSS.	1. Work demands 2. Work-family conflict 3. Insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers 4. Workplace violence and bullying 5. Organizational issues 6. Occupational hazards 7. Difficulty taking leave 8. Powerlessness 9. Unmet physiological needs	Ordinal (5-point Likert scale)	Mean and standard deviation
2. To describe the level of work resilience of nurses working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals according to RSN.	1. Philosophical pattern 2. Relational pattern 3. Situational pattern 4. Dispositional pattern	Ordinal (5-point Likert scale)	Mean and standard deviation
3. To determine the relationship between work stress and resilience of nurses working in extended working hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metropolitan Manila, Philippines.	1. Nurses' work stress 2. Nurses' work resilience	Ratio (p-value <0.05, 0.01, or 0.001)	Pearson Correlation and Spearman Rank Correlation
4. To determine the work stress of nurses who work extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic in their demographic profile.	1. Nurses' stress 2. Work demands 3. Work-family conflict 4. Insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers 5. Workplace violence and bullying 6. Organizational issues 7. Occupational hazards 8. Difficulty taking leave 9. Powerlessness 10. Unmet physiological need 11. Philosophical pattern 12. Relational pattern 13. Situational pattern 14. Dispositional pattern	Ratio (value of -1 to +1)	Pearson Correlation
5. To determine the work resilience of nurses who work extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic in their	1. Nurses' stress 2. Work demands 3. Work-family conflict 4. Insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers 5. Workplace violence and bullying 6. Organizational issues 7. Occupational hazards 8. Difficulty taking leave 9. Powerlessness 10. Unmet physiological need 11. Philosophical pattern 12. Relational pattern 13. Situational pattern 14. Dispositional pattern	Ratio (value of -1 to +1)	Pearson Correlation

Phase 1: Pre-Survey Phase

a. Pre-testing and Validation of the Survey Tool

Pilot testing of the survey tool in English was done online to assess the validity of the survey tool in the Philippine setting. A convenient sample of 10 nurses from different tertiary hospitals was asked to answer the online survey tool using Google Forms. The assessment was done after answering the survey tool with the following questions: (1) Are the questions easy to understand? (2) Are the items applicable to you?, (3) Are the questions stated clearly?, and (4) Can you understand the questions being asked? Participants in the work stress and resilience of nurses' survey pilot testing were not included in the main study. Internal consistency was determined by the computation of Cronbach's alpha.

Table 5

Reliability Statistics for Cronbach's Alpha

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
0.958	0.958	40

All 10 respondents answered yes to the assessment the result of Cronbach's alpha = 0.96 (out of 40 questions in the survey), Cronbach's alpha above 0.7 is considered reliable as shown in Table 5. My pilot testing showed a reliable result.

Table 6

Summary Item Statistics

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Maximum / Minimum	Variance	N of Items
Item Means	3.530	3.000	4.200	1.200	1.400	.083	40

The mean value for the pilot testing is 3.530 which is considered good in Table 6. (See Appendix G for the results of the pre-testing of the questionnaires).

b. Initial Engagement with the Participants

Coordination with the three tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila was done, specifically, the chief nurse and head of research and ethics committee for each hospital for permission to conduct the study and then to each unit of their hospital that renders direct care to COVID-19 patients.

The survey phase for nurses of Hospital A was on June 13 to 24, 2022. Hospital B and Hospital C were on February 1-15, 2023.

Phase 2: Survey Phase

Participants were asked to answer an online survey questionnaire. This survey included data collection on the demographic profile of the participants, the Nurses' Occupational Stress Scale Survey, and the Resilience Scale for Nurses Survey. Consent was collected online before proceeding with the survey.

The answered questionnaires did not go through any of the department heads, as this can be a source of coercion for the participant.

No participant withdrew from the study.

Data Management

Data is available to respondents upon request after processing and interpretation.

Data obtained were primarily stored in the researcher's personal Dell laptop computer and a backup was uploaded to the researcher's personal Google Cloud drive with a password connected to UP email and 64 GB Kingston silver thumb drive in case of data corruption and data loss of electronic devices. The data collected were stored in a safe file organizer and will be destroyed after five (5) years, by submerging the thumb drive in water with salt. All soft copies of responses saved in hard drives will be formatted to ensure complete deletion beyond recovery. All online copies of responses will be deleted as well. Questionnaires are ensured for completeness, consistency, and accuracy.

All data protection and collection comply with the Data Privacy Act 2012.

Data Analysis

Data were encoded using MS Excel for both descriptive and correlational statistics.

NOSS was used to describe the levels of work stress, mean, and standard deviation analysis using a 5-point Likert scale. These parameters were measured using the Likert scale such as Almost Always = 5, Very Often = 4, Sometimes = 3, Rarely = 2, Almost Never = 1. The higher the mean in each subscale, the higher the level of work stress among nurses who are working extended hours during the COVID-

19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila. Standard deviation was computed to determine the distribution pattern around the mean.

Similarly, the same descriptive statistics were computed to determine the levels of work resilience through its indicators. These parameters were measured using the same Likert scale.

Based on the result of mean and standard deviation, Pearson and Spearman rank correlation coefficient were used to determine the relationship between the level of work stress and level of work resilience to the frequency of extended working hours of nurses who rendered direct care to COVID-19 patients at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila. Proper interpretations and conclusions were made with the following expected results: a score of -1 indicates that the work stress and resilience of nurses who rendered direct care to COVID-19 cases has a negative correlation, zero (0) if there is no correlation, and +1 if there is a positive correlation between the two variables. Statistical significance of the correlation was determined if $p < 0.10$, $p < 0.05$, or $p < 0.01$.

ANOVA will be used to determine if there is a significant difference in work stress as the frequency of extended working hours as the month increases. Tukey-Kramer post hoc test will be used if there is an observed significant difference in ANOVA.

Ethical Considerations

This study was reviewed and approved by the Institutional Review Board of Hospital A, the Ethics Review Board of Hospital B, and the Institutional Review Board of Hospital C for the data collection adhering to the specific rules and regulations.

Consent from the participants was collected and information was given to them before the survey.

- I. Participants of the study were voluntary and were free to opt in or out of the study at any point in time.
- II. Participants' consent regarding the study was collected to let them know of the purpose, benefits, and risks before they agreed or declined to join.
- III. All data collected will remain anonymous during the study and will be kept confidential.
- IV. All information gathered was kept confidential and hidden from everyone else.
- V. The researcher ensures the study is free from plagiarism or research misconduct, and accurately represents the results.

Chapter 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

To complete this study properly, it is necessary to analyze the data collected to test the hypothesis and answer the research questions. This section discussed the results of the research following the discussions. This study was conducted from June 2022-February 2023 at the three tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila, Hospital A (46% of total respondents), Hospital B (45% of total respondents), and Hospital C (9% of total respondents) with 426 total distributed survey, only 128 total nurse respondents completed, and this was used to interpret the result. 128 nurse respondents experienced working extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic from February 1, 2021-January 31, 2022. The nurse's ages range from 21-59 years old with a median age of 40 years old, the majority are young adults (89.8%). As to sex, male and female nurse respondents comprise 36% and 64% respectively. Finally, the majority of the participants experience working extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic more than 5 times a month (41%), followed by 1-2 times a month (39%), and 3-5 times a month (20%).

The study has 128 nurse respondents, 89.8% consist of 21-40-year-old young adults and 10.2% are comprised of middle-aged adults. 64.1% of the respondents are made up of female nurses, while 35.9% are male nurses. In the criteria of marital status, 50.8% were married, 47.7% were single and 1.6% wouldn't say. In the educational criteria, 75% have a Baccalaureate Degree, 16.4% with Post-Baccalaureate Diploma, and 8.6% with Master's Degree. 82.8% of the 128 respondents have more than five (5) years of work experience, 8.6% of 3.08-5 years, and 8.6% of 1-3 years of work experience. In the hospital affiliation, 46.1% belonged

to Hospital A, while 44.5% to Hospital B, and 9.4% to Hospital C. In the criteria of the Area of Assignment, COVID-19 Ward has the highest percentage of 28.1%, next is the Emergency room which consists of 23.4%, COVID-19 ICU of 7%, COVID-19 OR of 6.3%, COVID-19 Pediatrics of 13.3%, and other area assignments which consists of 21.9%.

Lastly, the number of nurses with the frequency of working extended hours in a month consisting of 1-2 times a month is 41.4%, 3-5 times a month is 19.5%, and for those who extend work of more than 5 times a month 39.1%.

Shown in Table 7 is the summary of the participants' demographic data.

Table 7

Socio-Demographic Profile of Participants

CHARACTERISTICS	Frequency	Percentage
Socio-demographic Characteristics		
Age in years (median)	40	
21-40 (young adults)	115	89.8
41-59 (middle adults)	13	10.2
Sex		
Male	46	35.9
Female	82	64.1
<i>Marital Status</i>		
Single	61	47.7
Married	65	50.8
Others	2	1.6
<i>Educational attainment</i>		
Baccalaureate degree	96	75.0
Post-baccalaureate diploma	21	16.4
Master's degree	11	8.6
<i>Years of experience as a nurse</i>		
1-3 years	11	8.6
3.08-5 years	11	8.6
>5 years	106	82.8
Median in years	8.58	
Mode in years	10	
<i>Length of service at the current hospital</i>		
1-3 years	45	35.2
3.08-5 years	27	21.1
>5 years	56	43.8
Median in years	4.71	
Mode in years	6	
<i>Hospital affiliation of respondents</i>		
Hospital A	59	46.1
Hospital B	57	44.5
Hospital C	12	9.4
<i>Area of assignment</i>		
Emergency room	30	23.4
COVID-19 ICU	9	7.0
COVID-19 OR	8	6.3
COVID-19 Pedia	17	13.3
COVID-19 Ward	36	28.1
Others	28	21.9
<i>Frequency of Working in Extended Hours in a Month</i>		
1-2 times a month	53	41.4
3-5 times a month	25	19.5
More than 5 times a month	50	39.1

A. Level of work stress among nurses working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic using NOSS.

The level of work stress of nurses was measured using the NOSS questionnaire developed by Chen et al., 2020 to evaluate the stressors of nurses in Asia working at hospitals. The work stress of nurses was determined using a 21-item questionnaire with nine subscales. Table 6 shows the nine subscales of NOSS.

Table 8*Mean, Interpretation, and Standard Deviation of Items in NOSS*

NOSS item	Mean	SD
<i>Work Demands</i>		
3. I have to bear negative sentiments from patients or their relatives.	2.99	±1.14
5. I have to maintain professional units other than my own.	3.51	±1.08
11. Excessive duties in the workplace prevent me from attending to patients.	2.88	±1.08
Subscale Mean/SD	3.13	±1.13
<i>Work-Family Conflict</i>		
10. The burden of work makes it difficult for me to undertake my personal chores and/or engage in hobbies.	3.06	±1.08
20. The burden of work affects my domestic life.	2.91	±1.14
21. I have to adapt my schedule for family activities/outings to accommodate my work responsibilities.	3.67	±1.12
Subscale Mean/SD	3.22	±1.16
<i>Insufficient Support from Co-workers or Caregivers</i>		
12. I feel stressed because primary caregivers do not execute their tasks appropriately.	2.78	±1.03
13. Doctors' temperamental nature agitates me.	2.73	±1.05
15. I worry that my colleagues' incompetence will affect patient safety.	2.85	±1.07
Subscale Mean/SD	2.79	±1.04
<i>Workplace Violence and Bullying</i>		
16. I feel stressed due to psychological abuse such as threats, discrimination, bullying, and harassment.	2.45	±1.14
<i>Organizational Issues</i>		
4. The on-call system affects my life.	2.82	±1.23
6. Not achieving a promotion within the expected period affects my income.	2.45	±1.18
18. The organization usually remunerates my overtime work at a low rate of pay.	2.59	±1.26
Subscale Mean/SD	2.62	±1.23
<i>Occupational Hazards</i>		
1. I need to transport patients or equipment.	3.24	±1.21
19. I feel stressed considering that my patients might have contagious diseases such as COVID-19, SARS, or AIDS.	3.60	±1.14
Subscale Mean/SD	3.42	±1.19
<i>Difficulty Taking Leave</i>		
2. I cannot ask for leave for household emergencies.	2.48	±1.09
8. I cannot excuse myself for feeling strong discomfort.	2.86	±1.19
Subscale Mean/SD	2.67	±1.16
<i>Powerlessness</i>		
9. It upsets me if patients' conditions do not improve.	3.47	±1.06
17. I have insufficient time to offer mental health care to patients during working hours.	2.77	±1.10
Subscale Mean/SD	3.12	±1.13
<i>Unmet Basic Physiologic Need</i>		
7. I cannot take an uninterrupted 30-minute mealtime break.	2.93	±1.34
14. I have no time to fulfill my personal needs (e.g., water consumption and toilet breaks).	2.99	±1.12
Subscale Mean/SD	2.96	±1.23

Work Demands

NOSS subscale Work Demands had a mean of 3.13 ± 1.13 on the Likert scale which gives an interpretation that respondents were sometimes stressed working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Under the Work Demands subscale are question numbers 3 with a mean of 2.99 ± 1.14 (moderate level of stress), 5 with a mean of 3.51 ± 1.08 (high level of stress), and 11 with a mean of 2.88 ± 1.08 (moderate level of stress). The respondents in question number 3 reported a mean score of 2.99, which indicates a "moderate level of stress" (on average) when working extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. The standard deviation of ± 1.14 suggests that responses varied significantly around the mean, with some individuals experiencing higher stress levels and others experiencing lower stress levels. While question number 5 respondents reported a mean score of 3.51, which indicates a "high level of stress" (on average) when working extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. The standard deviation of ± 1.08 suggests that responses were relatively consistent, with most respondents experiencing a high level of stress for this particular question. Question number 11 respondents reported a mean score of 2.88, which indicates a "moderate level of stress" (on average) when working extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. The standard deviation of ± 1.08 suggests that responses varied significantly around the mean, similar to Question 3. The results imply that work demands can either promote growth and productivity, but can also be a greater cause for unproductivity among nurses. Work demands are significantly higher during the COVID-19 Pandemic. From this information, we can infer that participants perceived Question 5 to be associated with the highest level of stress (high level of stress), while Questions 3 and 11 were perceived to have a moderate level of stress. Overall, the data from the Work Demands subscale suggests that respondents, on average,

experienced moderate to high levels of stress when working extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. The variations in responses highlight that individuals' experiences with stress differed, with some reporting higher stress levels than others for specific questions. This is consistent with Al-Homayan et al., (2013) who reported that job demands can be challenging as a stressor and can promote growth and productivity among employees; on the other hand, they can also be unpleasant, undesirable, and excessive, which can be a hindrance to productivity.

Work-Family Conflict

NOSS subscale Work-Family Conflict had a mean of 3.22 ± 1.16 on the Likert scale which gives an interpretation that respondents were sometimes stressed working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Under the Work-Family Conflict subscale are question numbers 10 with a mean of 3.06 ± 1.08 (moderate level of stress), 20 with a mean of 2.91 ± 1.14 (moderate level of stress), and 21 with a mean of 3.67 ± 1.12 (high level of stress). In the Overall Work-Family Conflict, The mean score of 3.22 ± 1.16 suggests that, on average, respondents reported sometimes experiencing stress while working extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. The higher the mean value, the more frequently respondents experienced work-family conflict. In question number 10, with a mean score of 3.06 ± 1.08 , respondents reported a moderate level of stress specifically related to question 10. This item is about a specific aspect of work-family conflict, and the moderate level indicates that it was not as stressful as the overall average but still a notable concern for some respondents. The mean score of 2.91 ± 1.14 for question 20 also indicates a moderate level of stress for this particular aspect of work-family conflict. Similarly, it is below the overall mean, but still noteworthy for some respondents. With a mean score of $3.67 \pm$

1.12, respondents reported a high level of stress related to question 21. This item appears to be a significant source of work-family conflict during the COVID-19 pandemic for the respondents who participated in the survey. This is consistent with Sharma et al., (2016) that work-family conflict can also cause stress among nurses and its successive impact on their mental health.

Insufficient Support from Co-workers or Caregivers

NOSS subscale Insufficient Support from Co-workers or Caregivers had a mean of 2.79 ± 1.04 on the Likert scale which gives an interpretation that respondents were sometimes stressed working for extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Under the Insufficient Support from Co-workers or Caregivers subscale are question numbers 12 with a mean of 2.78 ± 1.03 (moderate level of stress), 13 with a mean of 2.73 ± 1.05 (moderate level of stress), and 15 with a mean of 2.85 ± 1.07 (moderate level of stress). This is congruent with Sodeify, Vanaki, & Mohammadi, (2013), who reported that the role of encouragement and support among nurses improves their performance at work and care for their clients.

Workplace Violence

NOSS subscale Workplace Violence with only one question number (16) had a mean of 2.45 ± 1.14 on the Likert scale which gives an interpretation that respondents have a very low level of stress working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. The respondents reported very little stress while working long hours during the COVID-19 epidemic, according to the mean of 2.45 on the Likert scale. Given the rather wide range of replies and the 1.14 standard deviation, it is clear that some respondents were more stressed than others. Overall, it was discovered that nurses

experienced very little stress related to workplace violence throughout the epidemic. The probability calculations are consistent with how the mean and standard deviation are interpreted. Given that there is a 0.6295 percent chance that a randomly chosen respondent had a stress level of 3 or above, almost 63% of respondents reported feeling little to no stress. According to the chance that a randomly chosen respondent had a stress level of 2 or lower, which is 0.307, 31% of respondents reported having very little stress. These results are positive because they imply that nurses were able to handle the pressure of putting in more hours during the pandemic. It is crucial to remember that this study was carried out in a particular nation and could not be transferable to other contexts. Furthermore, the study did not gather information on the particular forms of workplace violence that nurses encountered. There is a chance that nurses who were subjected to more extreme types of violence may have expressed more stress. Overall, the results of this study indicate that nurses who worked long hours during the COVID-19 epidemic reported very little stress. However, it is crucial to keep an eye on the situation and support nurses who could be under stress as a result of workplace violence. This is consistent with Zhang et al., (2018), who recommended the need for a harmonious work environment for nurses for the damage to health outcomes caused by workplace violence.

Organizational Issues

NOSS subscale Organizational Issues had a mean of 2.62 ± 1.23 on the Likert scale which gives an interpretation that respondents have a moderate level of stress working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Under the Organizational Issues subscale are question numbers 4 with a mean of 2.82 ± 1.23 (moderate level of stress), 6 with a mean of 2.45 ± 1.18 (low level of stress), and 18 with a mean of 2.59

± 1.26 (low level of stress). The respondents reported a moderate level of stress from working long hours during the COVID-19 pandemic as a result of inadequate organizational issues, according to the mean of 2.62 on the Likert scale. Given the rather wide range of replies and the 1.23 standard deviation, it is clear that some respondents were more stressed than others. The overall conclusion is that during the pandemic, nurses had a moderate amount of stress due to inadequate organizational concerns. The results are consistent with how the mean and standard deviation are interpreted. According to the probability that a randomly chosen respondent had a stress level of 3 or above, which is 0.551, almost 55% of respondents reported feeling moderately stressed out. There is a 0.449 percent chance that a randomly chosen respondent had a stress level of 2 or less, which indicates that roughly 45% of those who responded did so. All of these queries are connected to the experience of feeling abandoned by one's organization. As a result of feeling unappreciated or undervalued, this can be a major source of stress for nurses. Additionally, it could be challenging for them to do their duties efficiently, which might add to their stress. According to the study's findings, the COVID-19 pandemic caused moderate levels of stress among nurses due to inadequate organizational concerns. This is most likely a result of the pandemic's increased workload and stress on nurses. Organizations should make sure that nurses have access to the tools and assistance they need to handle these difficulties. This is consistent with Fallahi-Khoshknab, Ghavidel, Molavynejad, & Zarea, (2019), who reported that ineffective administrative approaches in the institution together with insufficient supply of equipment and human resources can lead to emotional exhaustion, stress, poorer service quality, high employee turnover, and early retirement of psychiatric nurses in Iran.

Occupational Hazards

NOSS subscale Occupational Hazards had a mean of 3.42 ± 1.19 on the Likert scale which gives an interpretation that respondents were very often stressed working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Under the Occupational Hazards subscale is question number 1 with a mean of 3.24 ± 1.21 (moderate level of stress) and 19 with a mean of 3.60 ± 1.14 (high level of stress). The respondents reported experiencing a very high degree of stress while working long hours during the COVID-19 pandemic because of occupational dangers, as indicated by the mean of 3.42 on the Likert scale. There was a rather wide range of replies, as indicated by the standard deviation of 1.19, with some respondents reporting higher levels of stress than others. Overall, it was discovered that nurses frequently expressed stress related to work-related risks throughout the pandemic. The results of this study imply that during the COVID-19 epidemic, nurses frequently underwent stress due to work dangers. This is probably brought on by the higher danger of exposure to injuries and infectious infections. Organizations must take action to safeguard nurses from these risks, including offering personal protective equipment and infection control training. This was also noted in the study of Hu, Luk, & Smith, 2015, that workplace hazard significantly contributes to the occurrence of stress or emotional exhaustion and depersonalization in nurses in Macau.

Difficulty Taking Leave

NOSS subscale Difficulty Taking Leave had a mean of 2.67 ± 1.16 on the Likert scale which gives an interpretation that respondents have a moderate level of stress working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Under the Difficulty Taking Leave subscale are question numbers 2 with a mean of 2.48 ± 1.09 (low level of stress) and 8 with a mean of 2.86 ± 1.19 (moderate level of stress). The respondents reported

a moderate amount of stress from working long hours during the COVID-19 epidemic because it was difficult to take time off, according to the mean of 2.67 on the Likert scale. Given the rather wide range of replies and the 1.16 standard deviation, it is clear that some respondents were more stressed than others. Overall, it was discovered that nurses had a moderate amount of stress as a result of their inability to take time off during the pandemic. This is supported by the study by Chen et al., (2020), which states the difficulty of taking leave for family-related reasons among Japanese nurses, adds to their burnout or worse death due to overwork. Japanese nurses feel guilty about taking leave without replacement because other nurses would be forced to compensate by working more hours.

Powerlessness

NOSS subscale Powerlessness had a mean of 3.12 ± 1.13 on the Likert scale which gives an interpretation that respondents have a moderate level of stress working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Under the Occupational Hazards subscale are question numbers 9 with a mean of 3.47 ± 1.06 (high level of stress) and 17 with a mean of 2.77 ± 1.10 (moderate level of stress). The respondents reported moderate levels of stress from working long hours during the COVID-19 epidemic because they felt helpless, according to the mean of 3.12 on the Likert scale. Given the rather wide range of replies and the 1.13 standard deviation, it is clear that some respondents were more stressed than others. Overall, it was discovered that nurses had a mild amount of stress as a result of feeling helpless in the face of the epidemic. This query relates to the experience of not having control over one's workplace. The feeling that they are not regarded or valued can be a big source of stress for nurses. Additionally, it could be challenging for them to do their duties efficiently, which might

add to their stress. The results of this study indicate that feeling helpless during the COVID-19 epidemic caused nurses to experience a moderate amount of stress. This is most likely a result of the pandemic's increased workload and stress on nurses. Organizations must provide nurses with more power with influence over their working environment. This is consistent with Davey et al., (2014), which showed in their study that Indian nurses were about 3 to 4 times more likely to experience professional stress due to poor and satisfactory doctor's attitudes towards them than to doctors with excellent attitudes.

Unmet Basic Physiologic Need

NOSS subscale Unmet Basic Physiologic Needs had a mean of 2.96 ± 1.23 on the Likert scale which gives an interpretation that respondents have a moderate level of stress working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Under the Occupational Hazards subscale are question numbers 7 with a mean of 2.93 ± 1.34 (moderate level of stress) and 14 with a mean of 2.99 ± 1.12 (moderate level of stress). This is supported by Cappelletti, Kreuter, Boyum, & Thompson, (2015), reported that basic physiological needs such as food, shelter, safety, and money can go unmet in economically disadvantaged populations and may yield adverse physical and mental health outcomes.

In the NOSS survey, nurse respondents were very often stressed due to the need to maintain professionalism in the workplace, adapting to the work schedule, the possibility of contracting infectious diseases, and if the patient's condition did not improve. According to the book published by Pope et al., 1995, working with life-threatening illnesses and injuries, demanding patients, overwork, understaffing, difficult schedules (i.e., rotating shifts or working multiple shifts), specialized

equipment, the hierarchy of authority, lack of control and participation in planning and decision making, and patient deaths are all workplace factors that may contribute to stress. Because of the depersonalization caused by a big bureaucratic system, nurses in many hospitals may feel alienated, weary, furious, and powerless (Pope et al., 1995).

In the NOSS survey, even if 115 out of 128 respondents, (89.8%) are 21-40 years old (young adults), and 64.1% (82 out of 128 respondents) are female, the result of work stress and resilience were not dictated by their differences in their sociodemographic.

Furthermore, based on the NOSS interpretation score in Appendix I, the data showed that nurses who had extended working hours for 1-2 times a month during the COVID-19 pandemic are rarely stressed due to insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers, workplace violence and bullying, difficulty taking leave, and unmet basic physiologic needs; furthermore, they are sometimes stressed due to work demands, work-family conflict, occupation hazards, and powerlessness. Nurses who had extended working hours for 3-5 times a month during the COVID-19 pandemic are rarely stressed due to workplace violence and bullying; they are sometimes stressed due to work demands, work-family conflict, insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers, organizational issues, difficulty taking leave, powerlessness, and unmet basic physiological needs; and they are often stressed due to occupational hazards. Lastly, nurses who had extended working hours for more than 5 times a month during the COVID-19 pandemic are sometimes stressed due to insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers, workplace violence and bullying, organizational issues, and difficulty taking leave; and they are often stressed due to work demands, work-family conflict, occupational hazards, powerlessness, and unmet basic physiological needs.

The results of Anova in Appendix J showed that there is an observed significant difference in the work stress level of nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic as the frequency of extended working hours increases, ($p = 6.79 \times 10^{-9}$) which supports the descriptive results of stress.

Using a *df* of 120 and a $q = 3.36$, based on the results of the Tukey-Kramer post hoc test in Appendix K, there is a significant difference between the work stress of nurses who worked 1-2 times a month of extended hours during COVID-19 pandemic versus those who worked 3-5 times a month, and more than 5 times a month. The level of work stress among nurses increases if they work more than two times a month for extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Similarly, Hoedl et al., 2021 did a study to assess the impact of nursing staff working hours during the COVID-19 pandemic on the perceived degree of stress. A statistically significant relationship was discovered between an increase in working hours and the degree of reported stress among nursing personnel (Hoedl et al., 2021).

On the other hand, there is no significant difference in the level of stress of nurses who worked extended hours 3-5 times a month versus those who worked more than 5 times a month.

Table 9*Mean, Interpretation, and Standard Deviation of Items in RSN*

RSN item	Mean	SD
<i>Philosophical Pattern</i>		
12. I have hope for the future.	4.21	±1.06
13. I feel generally happy.	3.87	±1.11
14. I am satisfied with my life.	3.80	±1.09
15. I am an important person.	3.90	±1.11
16a . I have strong goal consciousness for life.	4.04	±1.15
17. I am a necessary person to someone else.	3.88	±1.13
Subscale Mean/SD	3.95	±1.12
<i>Relational Pattern</i>		
3. I lead the conversation while considering the position of the other person.	3.63	±1.13
4. I keep a good relationship with the people around me.	4.20	±1.01
5. I fully accept the advice of others.	4.04	±1.01
6. There are people around me, to help when I have a difficult task.	3.88	±1.10
Subscale Mean/SD	3.95	±1.08
<i>Situational Pattern</i>		
7. I have the ability to determine the work that I can or cannot do.	4.07	±0.97
8. I have the ability to determine the priority order during the execution of the job.	4.02	±1.07
9. I know when I am not involved in the work, or I am involved.	4.05	±1.08
Subscale Mean/SD	4.04	±1.04
<i>Dispositional Pattern</i>		
1. I do not give up under any circumstances.	3.58	±1.45
2. I am a strong person and can cope with life's challenges and adversities.	4.01	±1.13
10. I have the ability to cope with stressful work situations.	3.96	±1.08
11. I can do a new job or difficult work.	3.93	±1.02
18. I am working autonomously.	3.76	±1.15
19. Once I start doing something, I can achieve the expected goal.	3.99	±1.03
Subscale Mean/SD	3.87	±1.16

Philosophical Pattern

RSN subscale Philosophical Pattern had a mean of 3.95 ±1.12 on the Likert scale which gives an interpretation that respondents have a high level of resilience working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Under the Philosophical Pattern subscale are question numbers 12 with a mean of 4.21 ±1.06 (very high level of resilience), 13 with a mean of 3.87 ±1.11 (high level of resilience), 14 with a mean of 3.80 ±1.09 (high level of resilience), 15 with mean of 3.90 ±1.11 (high level of resilience), 16 with mean of 4.04 ±1.15 (high level of resilience), and 17 with mean of 3.88 ±1.13 (high level of resilience).

Relational Pattern

RSN subscale Relational Pattern had a mean of 3.95 ± 1.08 on the Likert scale which gives an interpretation that respondents have a high level of resilience working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Under the Relational Pattern subscale are question numbers 3 with a mean of 3.63 ± 1.13 (high level of resilience), 4 with a mean of 4.20 ± 1.01 (high level of resilience), 5 with a mean of 4.04 ± 1.01 (high level of resilience), and 6 with mean of 3.88 ± 1.10 (high level of resilience).

Situational Pattern

RSN subscale Situational Pattern had a mean of 4.04 ± 1.04 on the Likert scale which gives an interpretation that respondents have a high level of resilience working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Under the Situational Pattern subscale are question numbers 7 with a mean of 4.07 ± 0.97 (high level of resilience), 8 with a mean of 4.02 ± 1.07 (high level of resilience), and 9 with a mean of 4.05 ± 1.08 (high level of resilience).

Dispositional Pattern

RSN subscale Dispositional Pattern had a mean of 3.87 ± 1.16 on the Likert scale which gives an interpretation that respondents have a high level of resilience working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic. Under the Dispositional Pattern subscale is question number 1 with a mean of 3.58 ± 1.45 (high level of resilience), 2 with a mean of 4.01 ± 1.13 (high level of resilience), 10 with mean of 3.96 ± 1.08 (high level of resilience), 11 with mean of 3.93 ± 1.02 (high level of resilience), 18 with mean of 3.76 ± 1.15 (high level of resilience), and 19 with mean of 3.99 ± 1.03 (high level of resilience).

Based on the RSN interpretation score in Appendix L, the data showed that nurses who had extended working hours regardless if it was 1-2 times, 3-5 times, or more than 5 times a month during the COVID-19 pandemic, were still very often resilient at work.

The results of ANOVA in Appendix M support the descriptive results of the work resilience of nurses in that there was no significant difference in the resilience of nurses to the frequency of extended working hours rendered in a month during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 10

Pearson Correlation and p-value of Work Stress and Resilience of Nurses according to their Demographics

Item	Coefficient (r)	N	T statistic	Degrees of freedom (df)	p-value
1. Work stress and resilience of nurses	-0.15	128	1.68	126	0.09
2. Work stress and resilience of Nurses ≤3 years at their current hospital during the COVID-19 pandemic	-0.34	45	2.38	43	0.02
3. Work stress and resilience of married nurses	-0.27	65	2.22	63	0.03
4. Work stress and resilience nurses assigned at COVID-19 ward, COVID-19 pediatrics, COVID-19 intensive care unit, and COVID-19 operating room	-0.32	70	2.82	68	0.006

The Pearson correlation coefficient (ρ) between work stress and resilience is -0.15, a negative relationship (see Figure 4). The p-value of the Pearson correlation is 0.09 [Table 8 (Item 1)] which is statistically significant at $p < 0.1$. Similar to Kannappan and Veigas's (2021) study "Perceived Stress and Resilience among Nurses Working

in a Selected Hospital in Mangalore," the findings revealed a weak correlation between perceived stress and resilience of nurses. The Pearson correlation and the correlation coefficient were used to determine the relationship between total perceived stress and total resilience, the result was 0.226 with a p-value of 0.071 (Kannappan & Veigas, 2021).

This research also used Spearman rank correlation, which quantifies strictly monotonic connections between two variables by ranking the data to convert a nonlinear strictly monotonic relationship to a linear relationship (Schober et al., 2018). Furthermore, this trait renders a Spearman coefficient very resistant to outliers (Schober et al., 2018). The Spearman rank correlation coefficient (ρ) of work stress and resilience result was -0.20458 (See Appendix N), a negative relationship. The p (2-tailed) = 0.02; by normal standards, the association between the two variables would be considered statistically significant. A related study by Rayani et al., 2021, showed that healthcare workers in southwest Iran had a significant negative relationship between anxiety and resilience during COVID-19 using a Spearman correlation test, which supports the results of this study using the same correlation.

Figure 4. Correlation of work stress and resilience of Nurses who worked extended hours during the COVID-19 Pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila

The Pearson correlation coefficient (ρ) between work stress and resilience yields a negative relationship (see Figure 5) among nurses who have worked three years or less at their current hospital during the COVID-19 pandemic in Table 8 (Item 2). The p-value of the Pearson correlation is 0.02 which is statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. While there are studies that correlate work stress and resilience in terms of the work experience of nurses, there are no studies found that correlate work stress and resilience in terms of work experience at their current hospital.

Figure 5. Correlation of work stress and resilience of nurses who worked in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic for three years and less at their current tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila

The Pearson correlation coefficient (ρ) between work stress and resilience yields a negative relationship (see Figure 6) among married nurses in Table 8 (Item 3). The p-value of the Pearson correlation is 0.03 which is statistically significant at $p < 0.05$. A similar finding was published in the study of Kannappan & Veigas, 2021, which showed that married nurses had moderate levels of stress and were less resilient compared to unmarried nurses in selected hospitals in Mangalore, India.

Figure 6. Correlation of work stress and resilience of married nurses who worked extended hours during the COVID-19 Pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila

The Pearson correlation coefficient (ρ) between work stress and resilience yields a negative (-0.32) relationship (see Figure 7) among nurses assigned to COVID-19 wards, COVID-19 pediatrics, COVID-19 intensive care units, and COVID-19 operating room in Table 8 (Item 4). The p-value of the Pearson correlation is 0.006 which is statistically significant at $p < 0.01$. The result is supported by the study of Khanmohammadi et al. in 2020, which stated most stressful factor for nurses on the COVID-19 ward was ambiguity about treatments, patients, and their families. Ward nurses' work stress grows as their resilience declines (Khanmohammadi et al., 2020). Resilience is a factor that influences ward nurse work stress (Khanmohammadi et al., 2020). The findings were further validated by Olaleye et al., 2022, who investigated

the association between burnout and resiliency among nurses in ICU settings, identifying resiliency as a buffer against the consequences of burnout. In addition to that, burnout is a significant factor in lowering the resilience of the operating room nurse, and it is also caused by workplace stress, night shift work, and excessive working pressure (Teymoori et al., 2022).

Figure 7. Correlation of work stress and resilience of nurses assigned at COVID-19 ward, COVID-19 pedia ward, COVID-19 ICU, and COVID-19 OR, and who worked in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila

Chapter 5

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

A descriptive-correlation design was utilized as the research design in this study involving nurses who worked for extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila. In coordination with the ethics committee of the three tertiary hospitals (Hospitals A, B, and C), nurses were surveyed online. With the use of a purposive sampling technique, participants were selected from each hospital. A total of 128 participants from the three tertiary hospitals consented to join the study. The results of the study showed the following:

Work Stress

The level of work stress among nurses who worked extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila was measured using the NOSS tool. The work stress level was determined using a 21-item questionnaire developed by Chen et al., 2020, which has nine subscales: (1) work demands, (2) work-family conflict, (3) insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers, (4) workplace violence and bullying, (5) organizational issues, (6) occupational hazards, (7) difficulty taking leave, (8) powerlessness, and (9) unmet basic physiological needs.

Based on the NOSS interpretation score in Appendix I, the data showed that as nurses increase the frequency of extended working hours in a month the more they get stressed due to work demands, work-family conflict, occupational hazards, powerlessness, and unmet basic physiological needs. This is supported by the results

of ANOVA in Appendix J as it showed that there is an observed significant difference in the work stress level of nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic as the frequency of extended working hours increases ($p=6.79 \times 10^{-9}$) which supports the descriptive results of stress. Furthermore, according to the Tukey-Kramer post hoc test results in Appendix K, there is a significant difference in job stress between nurses who worked 1-2 times per month of longer hours during the COVID-19 pandemic against those who worked 3-5 times per month and more than 5 times per month.

It is commonly known that work stress can result in ill health, injuries, and decreased well-being (Roberts & Grubb, 2015). The implications of work stress have been widely acknowledged, particularly for nurses (Roberts & Grubb, 2015). Work stress has been linked to lower job satisfaction, higher psychological discomfort, physical complaints, and absenteeism in this working population (Roberts & Grubb, 2015).

Work Resilience

Nursing work resilience must be regarded and recognized as a dynamic, fluid process that necessitates ongoing nurturing and dedication, as well as adaptation and flexibility in the face of shifting professional and personal demands (Henshall et al., 2020). System-level change is essential for resilience improvement interventions to be successful at the organizational, cultural, team, and managerial levels (Henshall et al., 2020). The level of work resilience among nurses who worked in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila was measured using the RSN tool. The work stress level was determined using a 19-item questionnaire developed by Park, Choi, & Kim, 2019. This study used four subscales

including 1) philosophical pattern, 2) relational pattern, 3) situational pattern, and 4) dispositional pattern.

Based on the RSN interpretation score in Appendix L, the data showed that the resilience of nurses remained the same despite an increase in the frequency of extended working hours in a month. The ANOVA results in Appendix M showed that there was no significant variation in nurses' work resilience level during the COVID-19 pandemic as the frequency of prolonged working hours increased ($p=0.69$), which supports the descriptive results of nurses' work resilience.

Correlation of Work Stress and Resilience

The initial results of Pearson correlation coefficient = -0.15 a negative relationship with $p = 0.09$ which is statistically significant at $p < 0.10$ and the result of Spearman rank correlation = -0.20 also a negative relationship with p (2-tailed) = 0.02 by normal standards, the association between the work stress and resilience of nurses working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic would be considered statistically significant. Furthermore, the Pearson correlation of work stress and resilience of nurses who worked extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals who are working for three years or less at their current hospital, those who are married, and those who are assigned to COVID-19 ward, COVID-19 pediatrics, and COVID-19 OR/ICU all have a negative relationship and have p -values of 0.02, 0.03, and 0.006 respectively which all translate to be statistically significant. Many medical personnel, particularly nurses, are battling in the medical industry as a result of the recent COVID-19 outbreak (Kim & Chang, 2022). Several studies have been published that demonstrate that enduring this difficult scenario has reduced the resilience of nurses in several countries (Kim & Chang, 2022).

On the other hand, nurses in ER ($\rho=0.07$, $p=0.71$) and nurses in other areas ($\rho=0.08$, $p=0.69$) showed no statistical significance in the correlation of work stress to their resilience during the COVID-19 pandemic. These findings are supported by the study of Elder et al., 2019 when faced with work pressures, ER practitioners employ a variety of coping techniques, as observed in our study. Only a few respondents in the survey used maladaptive coping mechanisms, with the majority using more positive or adaptive tactics (Elder et al., 2019). ER practitioners are more prone to use maladaptive or negative coping techniques than practitioners in other clinical fields such as pediatrics and women's health (Elder et al., 2019). Chronic stress, as well as the sort of coping techniques used, has been connected to disengagement from work, as well as the development of compassion fatigue and burnout (Elder et al., 2019).

Conclusion

The findings of the study showed that the nurses' work stress has a negative relationship with their resilience when working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metro Manila; furthermore, nurses who more frequently worked in extended hours are more likely to get stressed due to work demands, work-family conflict, occupational hazards, powerlessness, and unmet basic physiological needs. There is also a negative relationship and statistical significance of work stress and resilience among nurses, who have worked three years or less at their current hospital, are married, and/or assigned to COVID-19 ward, COVID-19 pedia, COVID-19 ICU and COVID-19 OR, during the COVID-19 pandemic regardless of the frequency of their extended working hours in a month, affiliation, sex, educational attainment, religion, and age.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study, the following may be recommended:

1. Since the study was done during the COVID-19 pandemic. It is suggested that a similar investigation be done with larger sample sizes and control groups after the COVID-19 pandemic.
2. It is observed that there is a negative correlation between work stress to resilience of the majority of respondents, it would be advisable for hospital administrations and policymakers to limit the working hours of nurses to up to 40 hours a week as much as possible to prevent work stress and reduction of work resilience among nurses especially during a pandemic.
3. It is recommended to hospital administrators that the demographics mentioned above who have a negative relationship between work stress and resilience should be prioritized for intervention to lessen job turnover.
4. Future studies may focus on assessing and creating a validated resilience scale for nurses that would be more applicable to Filipinos and would more likely explain the high job turnover and migration. Future studies may also include nurses who have already resigned from work or those who are already working outside the Philippines.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A

NOSS Authorization

Letter of Authorization

November 5, 2021

Dear Mr. Gian Rei A. Mangcucang,

Thank you for your recent inquiry regarding the Nurses' Occupational Stressor Scale (NOSS) authorization. We hereby authorize you to use the NOSS in your research, entitled "Work Stress and Resilience Among Nurses on Working on Extended Hours During COVID-19 Pandemic in Tertiary Hospitals in Metro Manila". Attached please find the published paper of the development of NOSS, for your reference.

We wish you every success in your future endeavors.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to be 'Judith SC Shiao', written over a horizontal line.

Judith SC Shiao (RN; PhD)
Professor
School of Nursing, College of Medicine, National Taiwan University
Honorary Professor
Sydney Nursing School, University of Sydney
Email: scshiao@ntu.edu.tw

Appendix B

RSN Authorization

From: 박성희
Sent: Saturday, November 6, 2021 7:32 PM
To: Gian Rei Mangcucang
Subject: [RE]Request for academic use of Resilience Scale for Nurses

Dear

Thank you for your interest in our tools. We hope our tools will help you in writing your master's thesis. You can also use tools. I wish you good results.

Sincerely,

Sunghee Park

Sunghee Park

Department of Nursing
Kunsan National University

----- Original Message -----

From : Gian Rei Mangcucang <gamangcucang@up.edu.ph>
To : <shpark@kunsan.ac.kr>
Cc :
Sent : 2021-11-06 15:14:33
Subject : Request for academic use of Resilience Scale for Nurses

Dear Mr./Ms. Sunghee Park:
Good day!

I would like to request your good office to allow me to use the Resilience Scale for Nurses Tool (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apnu.2018.12.004>) for my master's thesis at University of the Philippines Open University.

My thesis entitled: "Work Stress and Resilience Among Nurses Working on Extended Hours During COVID-19 Pandemic in Tertiary Hospitals in Metropolitan Manila, Philippines"

Your most favorable response is highly appreciated. Thank you.

Respectfully yours,

--

Gian Rei A. Mangcucang, RN, EMT, DIH
Master of International Health Student
Faculty of Management and Development Studies
University of the Philippines Open University

Appendix C

QR Code for Online Survey

**PLEASE SCAN CODE FOR ONLINE VERSION OF
SURVEY OR TYPE THE URL BELOW**

Appendix D

Online Survey

Questionnaire

7/5/22, 6:05 PM

Work Stress and Resilience of Nurses Survey

Work Stress and Resilience of Nurses Survey

I, Gian Rei A. Mangucang is conducting a study on Work Stress and Work Resilience of Nurses Working on Extended Hours During the COVID-19 Pandemic at Tertiary Hospitals in Metro Manila, Philippines, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of Master of International Health in University of the Philippines Open University.

The results of the study may reveal the relationship of work stress to work resilience of nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings are expected to benefit the following: the nurses, clients, the institutions, other health facilities, future researchers, entire health community.

The main purpose of the study is to determine the relationship between work stress and work resilience among nurses working extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic at tertiary hospitals in Metropolitan Manila, Philippines.

The study specifically seeks to answer the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of work stress of nurses working in extended hours during COVID-19 pandemic in tertiary hospitals according to Nurses' Occupational Stressor Scale (NOSS):
 - i. Work demands
 - ii. Work-family conflict
 - iii. Insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers
 - iv. Workplace violence and bullying
 - v. Organizational issues
 - vi. Occupational hazards
 - vii. Difficulty taking leave
 - viii. Powerlessness
 - ix. Unmet physiological needs
2. To describe the level of work resilience of the nurses working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic in tertiary hospitals according to the Resilience Scale for Nurses (RSN):
 - i. Philosophical pattern
 - ii. Relational pattern
 - iii. Situational pattern
 - iv. Dispositional pattern
3. To determine the relationship of work stress and work resilience of nurses working in extended working hours during the COVID-19 pandemic in tertiary hospitals in Metropolitan Manila, Philippines.

The study will use purposive sampling of nurses who rendered direct care to COVID-19 cases specifically to the five to five (5) JCI-accredited and DOH hospitals in Metro Manila, Philippines, both private and public. The department heads will determine who is qualified to be a respondent for the study.

The study is aimed to be conducted in a 1-week time frame. Surveys are expected to be answered by the respondents in a week, for the researcher to be able to collate and gather the data from the survey. The respondents are expected to answer the survey as honestly and as accurately as possible. Since the survey will be answered online, and not on-site, the hospital representative's function is limited to recruiting qualified participants to answer the survey.

The study also aims to use the information from the data collected to be used by the hospital and nursing administrators in decision-making for implementing interventions for the mental well-being of nurses and improving the work environment, especially during pandemics or surges of emerging and reemerging infectious diseases. This will also help hospital administrators improve the work environment and benefits given to Nurses.

Names and all other private information shall remain confidential to the researcher. All data collected from the study are in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

The respondents can withdraw anytime from the study if they feel vulnerable. The respondents should send an email or private message to the researcher informing him of the withdrawal. The withdrawal shall take

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1hf2fvN78J6dWMr1y6Irt30CuhKVJKN2OqoDJFVBQY/edit>

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effect immediately.

For questions, clarifications, and other concerns, please don't hesitate to send us a message at gianrei.mangcucang@upou.edu.ph or message at 0999 995 5161.

This proposal has been reviewed and approved by Dr. Froilan Jacinto R. Obillo, MD, FPCP, Chair, ARMMC-ERB, which is a committee whose task it is to make sure that research participants are protected from harm. If you wish to find out more about the ERB, please contact Ms. Thelma A. Fadallan, ARMMC-ERB Secretariat at 941-5854 loc. 266.

*** Required**

1. Informed Consent Form: By participating in this survey, you hereby agree and provide consent * the collection of data: "I have read this form or had this form read to me about the purpose of the survey and its possible risks and benefits. I have been able to ask questions about the survey and have had my questions answered. I understand that I can refuse to participate in this survey, even after signing this form, and it will not affect my employment status. I understand that the purpose of the survey is to determine the work stress and work resilience of nurses working in extended hours during the COVID-19 pandemic and that my participation is voluntary." Thank you for you participation! Do you agree to participate in the survey?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
 No

Demographic Data

2. Sex *

Mark only one oval.

- Male
 Female
 Other: _____

3. Age *

4. Hospital affiliation *

Mark only one oval.

- Quirino Memorial Medical Center, Quezon City
- Amang Rodriguez Memorial Medical Center, Marikina City
- St. Luke's Medical Center Global City
- St. Luke's Medical Center Quezon City
- The Medical City, Pasig City
- Jose R. Reyes Memorial Medical Center, Manila
- Other: _____

5. Area of assignment *

Mark only one oval.

- Emergency room
- COVID-19 pedia
- COVID-19 ward
- COVID-19 ICU
- COVID-19 OR
- COVID-19 DR
- Swabbing area
- Other: _____

6. Marital status *

Mark only one oval.

- Married
- Single
- Annuled/Divorced
- Widowed

7. Educational attainment *

Mark only one oval.

- Baccalaureate degree
- Post-baccalaureate (diploma) degree
- Master's degree
- Doctoral degree

8. Religion *

9. Length of service in current work *

In years and months

10. Length of service as nurse *

In years and months

11. Job level *

Mark only one oval.

- Probation
- Jr. staff nurse
- Sr. staff nurses
- Head nurse/assistant unit manager
- Manager
- Other: _____

12. Have experienced more than 8-hour duty during the COVID-19 pandemic *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

Part I: Nurses' Occupational Stressor Scale

Please select the best correspond to your perception.

13. Please select the best choice that corresponds to your perception during the time you have worked in extended hours due to the COVID-19 pandemic between February 1, 2021 to January 31, 2022. *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Almost never	Rarely	Sometimes	Very Often	Almost always
I need to transport patients or equipment.	<input type="radio"/>				
I cannot ask for leaves for household emergencies	<input type="radio"/>				
I have to bear negative sentiment from patients or their relatives	<input type="radio"/>				
The on-call system affects my life.	<input type="radio"/>				
I have to maintain professional units other than my own.	<input type="radio"/>				
Not achieving promotion within expected period affects my income.	<input type="radio"/>				
I cannot take an uninterrupted 30-minute mealtime break.	<input type="radio"/>				
I cannot excuse myself for feeling strong discomfort.	<input type="radio"/>				
It upsets me if patients' condition do not improve.	<input type="radio"/>				
The burden of work makes it difficult for me to undertake my personal chores and/or engage in hobbies.	<input type="radio"/>				
Excessive duties in the workplace prevent me from attending to patients.	<input type="radio"/>				
I feel stressed because primary	<input type="radio"/>				

caregivers do not execute their tasks appropriately.

Doctors' temperamental nature agitates me.

<input type="radio"/>				
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I have no time to fulfill my personal needs (e.g., water consumption and toilet breaks).

<input type="radio"/>				
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I worry that my colleagues' incompetence will affect patient safety.

<input type="radio"/>				
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I feel stressed due to psychological abuse such as threats, discrimination, bullying, and harassment.

<input type="radio"/>				
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I have insufficient time to offer mental health care to patients during working hours.

<input type="radio"/>				
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

The organization usually remunerates my overtime work at a low rate of pay.

<input type="radio"/>				
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I feel stressed considering that my patients might have contagious diseases such as COVID-19, SARS, or AIDS.

<input type="radio"/>				
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

The burden of work affects my domestic life.

<input type="radio"/>				
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

I have to adapt my schedule for family activities/outings to accommodate my work responsibilities.

<input type="radio"/>				
-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------	-----------------------

Part II: Resilience Scale for Nurses

14. Please select the best choice that corresponds to your perception during the time you have * worked in extended hours due to the COVID-19 pandemic February 1, 2021 to January 31, 2022.

Mark only one oval per row.

	Almost never	Rarely	Sometimes	Very often	Almost always
I do not give up under any circumstances.	<input type="radio"/>				
I am a strong person and can cope with life's challenges and adversity.	<input type="radio"/>				
I lead the conversation while considering the position of the other person.	<input type="radio"/>				
I keep a good relationship with people around me.	<input type="radio"/>				
I fully accept the advice of others.	<input type="radio"/>				
There are people around me, to help when I have a difficult task	<input type="radio"/>				
I have the ability to determine the work that I can do or cannot do.	<input type="radio"/>				
I have the ability to determine the priority order during the execution of the job.	<input type="radio"/>				
I know when I am not involved in the work or I am involved.	<input type="radio"/>				
I have the ability to cope with stressful work situations.	<input type="radio"/>				
I can do a new job or a difficult work.	<input type="radio"/>				
I have hope for the future.	<input type="radio"/>				
I feel generally happy.	<input type="radio"/>				

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Work Stress and Resilience of Nurses Survey

I am satisfied with my life.	<input type="radio"/>				
I am an important person.	<input type="radio"/>				
I have strong goal consciousness for life.	<input type="radio"/>				
I am a necessary person to someone else.	<input type="radio"/>				
I am working autonomously.	<input type="radio"/>				
Once I start doing something, I can achieve the expected goal.	<input type="radio"/>				

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Google Forms

<https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1hfi2fvN78J6dWMr1y6Irt30CuhKVtJKN2OqoDJFVBQY/edit>

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Appendix E

Letter of Request to Conduct Survey

GIAN REI A. MANGCUCANG, RN

University of the Philippines Open University | Faculty of Management and Development Studies |
Master of International Health | 0977 263 8080 | gamangcucang@up.edu.ph

[Date]

[Recipient Name]

[Title]

Hospital Name

[Street Address]

[City, ST Zip Code]

Dear [Recipient Name]

Greetings!

The name signed below is conducting a study on, **Work Stress and Resilience of Nurses Working on Extended Hours During the COVID-19 Pandemic at Tertiary Hospitals in Metro Manila, Philippines**, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Master of International Health.

The results of the study may reveal the relationship of work stress to resilience of nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings are expected to benefit the following: the nurses, clients, the institutions, other health facilities, future researchers, entire health community.

Of this matter, may I ask permission to conduct study in your hospital? If you have any question or concerns, you may reach me via my mobile number or my email.

Your most favorable response is highly appreciated.

Sincerely,

Gian Rei A. Mangcucang, RN
Researcher

Appendix F.

Socio-Demographic Profile of Participants for Pre-test Survey

CHARACTERISTICS	Frequency	Percentage
Socio-demographic Characteristics		
Age in years (median)	10	
21-40 (young adults)	10	100.0
41-59 (middle adults)	0	0.0
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	6	60.0
Female	4	40.0
<i>Marital Status</i>		
Single	9	90.0
Married	1	10.0
Others	0	0.0
<i>Educational attainment</i>		
Baccalaureate degree	6	60.0
Post-baccalaureate diploma	3	30.0
Master's degree	11	8.6
<i>Years of experience as nurse</i>		
1-3 years	1	10.0
3.08-5 years	2	20.0
>5 years	7	70.0
Median in years	6.75	
Mode in years	12	
<i>Length of service at current hospital</i>		
1-3 years	3	30.0
3.08-5 years	2	20.0
>5 years	5	50.0
Median in years	4.79	
Mode in years	6	
<i>Hospital affiliation of respondents</i>		
Asklepios Fachklinikum Stadtroda GmbH	1	10.0
Oriental Mindoro Provincial Hospital	1	10.0
Marinduque Provincial Hospital	1	10.0
ARMMC, Marikina City	4	40.0
St. Luke's Medical Center, Taguig City	3	30.0
<i>Area of assignment</i>		

Emergency room	5	50.0
COVID-19 ICU	0	0.0
COVID-19 OR	0	0.0
COVID-19 Pedia	0	0.0
COVID-19 Ward	3	30.0
Others	2	20.0
<i>Frequency of Working in Extended Hours in a Month</i>		
1-2 times a month	1	10.0
3-5 times a month	3	30.0
More than 5 times a month	6	60.0

Appendix G

Cronbach's Alpha using SPSS

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	10	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	10	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Scale Statistics

Mean	Variance	Std. Deviation	N of Items
141.2000	679.511	26.06743	40

Appendix H

Sample Size Calculation

Sample size formula

$$\text{Sample size} = \frac{\frac{[(z^2)(p)](1-p)}{e^2}}{1 + \left\{ \frac{[(z^2)(p)](1-p)}{e^2 N} \right\}}$$

N = population size

e = Margin of error (percentage in decimal form)

Z = Z-score

p = sample proportion

Desired confidence level	z-score
80%	1.28
85%	1.44
90%	1.65
95%	1.96
99%	2.58

Sample size using calculator

Online surveys with Vovici have completion rates of 66%!

Alternate scenarios		
With a sample size of	100	200
Your margin of error would be	8.98%	6.34%
	300	
	5.18%	
With a confidence level of	90	95
Your sample size would need to be	89	126
		218

Save effort, save time. Conduct your survey online with Vovici.

Appendix I

Mean and standard deviation of Work Stress among Nurses' Frequency of Working in Extended Hours using the nine subscales of NOSS in relation to frequency of extended working hours in a month

Subscales	1-2 times a month mean	3-5 times a month mean	>5 times a month mean	Overall mean	SD
Work demands	2.65	3.37	3.51	3.13	±1.13
Work-family conflict	2.82	3.39	3.55	3.22	±1.16
Insufficient support from coworkers or caregivers	2.48	2.79	3.11	2.79	±1.04
Workplace violence and bullying	2.02	2.32	2.98	2.45	±1.14
Organizational issues	2.03	2.68	3.25	2.62	±1.23
Occupational hazards	2.89	3.80	3.80	3.42	±1.19
Difficulty taking leave	2.27	2.74	3.05	2.67	±1.16
Powerlessness	2.81	3.18	3.42	3.12	±1.13
Unmet basic physiological needs	2.54	2.86	3.46	2.96	±1.23

Appendix J

Anova: Single Factor of Work Stress using NOSS for working in extended hours 1-2 times a month, 3-5 times a month, and >5 times a month

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
1-2 times a month	53	133.7143	2.522911	0.273809
3-5 times a month	25	83.14286	3.325714	0.731799
>5 times a month	50	168.3333	3.366667	0.596441

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	F crit
Between Groups	21.42693	2	10.71346	21.94416	6.79x10 ⁻⁹	3.068689
Within Groups	61.02685	125	0.488215			
Total	82.45378	127				

Appendix K

Tukey-Kramer post-hoc test of Anova results of work stress of nurses in relation to frequency of extended working hours in a month

Group 1	Group 2	Difference	<i>n</i> (Group 1)	<i>n</i> (Group 2)	SE	q	Result
1-2 times a month	3-5 times a month	0.802803	53	25	0.120	6.697	Significant difference
3-5 times a month	>5 times a month	0.040952	25	50	0.121	0.338	No significant difference
>5 times a month	1-2 times a month	0.843756	50	53	0.097	8.662	Significant difference

Appendix L

Mean scores and standard deviation of Work Resilience among Nurses Working in Extended Hours using the four subscales of RSN in relation to frequency of extended working hours in a month

Subscales	1-2 times a month mean	3-5 times a month mean	>5 times a month mean	Overall mean	SD
Philosophical pattern	3.97	4.05	3.88	3.95	±1.12
Relational pattern	3.96	4.09	3.84	3.94	±1.08
Situational pattern	4.04	4.01	4.07	4.04	±1.04
Dispositional pattern	3.83	4.05	3.82	3.87	±1.16

Appendix M

Anova: Single Factor of Work Resilience using RSN for working in extend hours 1-2 times a month, 3-5 times a month, and >5 times a month

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
1-2 times a month	53	208.5789	3.935452	0.705694
3-5 times a month	25	101.3158	4.052632	0.385734
>5 times a month	50	194	3.88	0.785804

Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	p-value	F crit
Between Groups	0.49683	2	0.248415	0.36766	0.693098	3.068689
Within Groups	84.45807	125	0.675665			
Total	84.9549	127				

Appendix N

Spearman rank correlation of work stress and resilience

Coefficient (r):	-0.20458
N:	128
T statistic:	2.34601
<i>df</i> :	126
p value:	0.020537

Appendix O

Good Clinical Practice Certificate

Appendix P

Approval of Thesis Proposal Oral Defense

UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES OPEN UNIVERSITY

FACULTY OF MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT STUDIES

Date: _____

DR. JOANE V. SERRANO

Dean, Faculty of Management and Development Studies
UP Open University

Through PROPER CHANNELS

Dear Dean Serrano:

We have the honor to inform you that the undersigned served in the thesis proposal oral defense of **GIAN REI A. MANGCUCANG, MASTER OF INTERNATIONAL HEALTH** candidate who presented *name of student* *degree/track/major* his/her thesis defense entitled "Work Stress and Work Resilience of Nurses Working on Extended Hours During COVID-19 Pandemic in Tertiary Hospitals in Metro Manila, Philippines" on **March 15, 2022, 10am.** at *date and time*

UP Open University Headquarters, Los Baños, Laguna.
venue

Faculty of Management and Development Studies, UP Open University and voted as follows:
degree-granting unit

PANEL MEMBERS	FOR APPROVAL	FOR DISAPPROVAL
 ASST. PROF. QUEENIE ROXAS- RIDULME Panel Chair/Adviser	_____	_____
 DR. EVELYN VICTORIA RESIDE Critic	_____	_____
 ASSOC. PROF. MYRA D. ORUGA Member	_____	_____
 ASST. PROF. MA. ELMA MIRANDILLA Member	_____	_____
 DR. JOSEPHINE AGAPITO Member	_____	_____

Committee's Decision:

() PASSED

() FAILED

Additional

Remark/s: _____ **Approved on the provisions of addressing the comments of the thesis guidance committee**

Very truly yours,

ASSOC. PROF. MYRA D. ORUGA
Thesis Panel Chair/Adviser
Program Chair, MIH

Appendix Q

Endorsement Form from Unit Head

	UP OPEN UNIVERSITY Institutional Research Ethics Committee		
	ENDORSEMENT FORM FROM UNIT HEAD		REC Form No. 6 (B)
			Version No: 01
			Date of Effectivity:

1. General Information			
*Studies endorsed for Research Review	Work Stress and Work Resilience of Nurses Working in Extended Hours During COVID-19 Pandemic in Tertiary Hospitals in Metro Manila, Philippines		
*Name of Researcher	MANGCUCANG, GIAN REI ABAD	Contact Information of corresponding author	*Tel No: 02-89525331
			*Mobile No: 0999 995 5161
*Co-researcher (if any)	N/A		Fax No:
			*Email gianrei.mangcucang@upou.edu.ph
2. Technical panels who reviewed the paper			
Office/Dept	Name UPOU FMDS		
	1) DR. MYRA D. ORUGA		
	2) ASST. PROF. ELMA MIRANDILLA		
	3) ASST. PROF. JOSEPHINE AGAPITO		
3. Endorsement			
*Department/Program	FMDS/ MASTER OF INTERNATIONAL HEALTH		
*Unit Head	DR. MYRA D. ORUGA		
*Signature			
*Date	25 April 2022		

Appendix R

Approval Letter from JRRMMC IRB

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Health
JOSE R. REYES MEMORIAL MEDICAL CENTER
Rizal Avenue, Sta. Cruz, Manila 1003
7321071-76 loc. 296 <http://www.jrrmmc.org> jrrmmc.irb@gmail.com

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD

Form 2.7

APPROVAL LETTER

July 27, 2022

This is to certify that the following protocol and related documents have been granted approval by the Jose R. Reyes Memorial Medical Center IRB for implementation.

IRB Protocol No.	2022-085	Sponsor Protocol No.	N/A
Principal Investigator/s	Mr. GIAN REI MANGCUCANG, DipIH, RN, EMT-B	Sponsor	N/A
Title	Work stress and work resilience among nurses working in extended hours during Covid-19 pandemic in tertiary hospitals in Metropolitan Manila, Philippines		
Protocol Version No.	Version 1	Version Date	July 5, 2022
ICF Version No.	Version 1	Version Date	July 5, 2022
Other Documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Summary of Revision Form Revised Protocol 		
Type of Review	<input type="checkbox"/> Expedited <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Full board Approval date: July 27, 2022	Duration of Approval: July 27, 2022 July 26, 2023	Frequency of Continuing Review: Once a year

Investigator Responsibilities after Approval:

- Submit document amendments for IRB approval before implementing them.
- Submit SAE and SUSAR reports to the IRB within 7 days.
- Submit progress report every 12 months.
- Submit final report after completion of protocol procedures at the study site.
- Report protocol deviation/violation.
- Comply with all relevant international and national guidelines and regulations.
- Abide by the principles of good clinical practice and ethical research.
- This approval is valid for a period of one year from the date of issue. Therefore, the PI must re-apply for continuing ethics review.

*The Jose R. Reyes Memorial Medical Center Institutional Review Board is organized and operates according to the **Good Clinical Practice** and all applicable laws and regulations.*

IRB Chairperson	Signature	Date
MICHELLE Y. OTAYCO, MD, FPCP, FPSN, MMHoA		07/27/2022

Received by:

Name & Signature: _____

Date: _____

Appendix S

Approval Letter from ARMMC ERB

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Health
'AMANG' RODRIGUEZ MEMORIAL MEDICAL CENTER
Sumulong Highway, Sto. Niño, Marikina City, Philippines 1800
Email Address: amangrod@yahoo.com / Website: www.armmc.doh.gov.ph
Tel. Nos. (+632) 941-5854 & (+632) 948-1263
"PHIC Accredited"

ETHICS REVIEW BOARD (Comm. Form 2.02)

December 12, 2022

MR. GIAN REI A. MANGCUCANG
Principal Investigator
University of the Philippines Open University

RE: PROTOCOL EVALUATION

Dear **Mr. Mangcucang**,

We wish to inform you that the ARMMC-ERB has reviewed your protocol and has granted its approval for implementation, to wit:

ARMMC-ERB Protocol No:	TP-2022-11-00
Sponsor Protocol No:	N/A
Research/Project Title:	Work Stress and Work Resilience Among Nurses Working in Extended Hours During the COVID-19 Pandemic at Tertiary Hospitals in Metropolitan Manila Philippines
Approval Date:	December 9, 2022
Expiration Date:	December 8, 2023
Type of Approval:	<input type="checkbox"/> Expedited <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Full Review

Please be reminded that after this approval, the following are your responsibilities:

1. This approval expires on the date indicated above. For renewal, submit to us a Progress Report every six months/year (use *Form 3.05*);
2. Inform the ERB of any modifications or changes in the research design which affect human participants, or changes in consent documents, prior to implementation (use *Form 3.03*);
3. Report to us any protocol deviation / violation (use *Form 3.07*);
4. Submit SAE (*serious adverse event*) and SUSAR (*suspected unexpected serious adverse reaction*) reports within seven days of the occurrence of the event (use *Form 3.02*);
5. Upon completion of the study, inform us in writing by submitting a Final Accomplishment Report (*Form 3.06*);

You are to comply with all international and national guidelines and regulations, and abide by the principles of good clinical practice and ethical research.

For your information and guidance.

MARIA GRACIA CONCEPCION C. VESAGAS, MD, FPCS
OIC, Ethics Review Board

Republic of the Philippines
 Department of Health
'AMANG' RODRIGUEZ MEMORIAL MEDICAL CENTER
 Marikina City
 "PHIC Accredited"

**ETHICS REVIEW BOARD
 ACTION DECISION (Form 2.08)**

ARMMC-ERB Control No:	TP-2022-11-00
Sponsor Protocol No:	N/A
Review Date:	December 9, 2022

Protocol Title: **Work Stress and Work Resilience Among Nurses Working in Extended Hours During the COVID-19 Pandemic at Tertiary Hospitals in Metropolitan Manila Philippines**

Type of Submission:

<input type="checkbox"/> Initial Review	<input type="checkbox"/> Continuing Review
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Resubmission for re-review	<input type="checkbox"/> Protocol Termination
<input type="checkbox"/> Protocol Amendment(s)	<input type="checkbox"/> Final Report

Type of Review:

<input type="checkbox"/> Expedited	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Full Board Review
<input type="checkbox"/> SJREB	<input type="checkbox"/> Exempt

ARMMC-ERB Decision

<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Approved
<input type="checkbox"/> Minor revisions required
<input type="checkbox"/> Major revisions required
<input type="checkbox"/> More information required
<input type="checkbox"/> Others

Name of OIC MARIA GRACIA CONCEPCION C. VESAGAS, MD, FPCS	Signature
Date December 12, 2022	

ERB – Action Decision Rev. 1
 07 September 2018
 Page: 1 of 1

Appendix T

Approval Letter from TMC IRB

10 January 2023

Gian Rei A. Mangcucang, DipIH, RN, EMT-B
Principal Investigators
The Medical City

Protocol Title: **Work Stress and Work Resilience Among Nurses Working in Extended Hours During COVID-19 Pandemic at Tertiary Hospitals in Metropolitan Manila, Philippines**

Re: **Research Approval**

Dear Sir Mangcucang,

This is to inform you that the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of this hospital **grants an approval** of the document, as mentioned above. The study was initially reviewed on **16 August 2022** and subsequent documents were approved on **10 January 2023** at the IRB Office, Medical Library, Podium Building, The Medical City.

This approval is valid until **10 January 2024**. It is understood that a copy of your final paper must be submitted upon the completion of the study. The approved versions of the document are listed in the attached **Annex 1.0**.

We confirm that we are an Ethics Committee constituted in agreement and accordance with the guidelines of the International Conference on Harmonization of Good Clinical Practice (ICH-GCP).

Sincerely,

Gemin Louis C. Apostol, MD, MBA
Panel Secretary
Institutional Review Board

Carlo Emmanuel J. Surpaico, MD
Chair
Institutional Review Board

Ortigas Avenue, Pasig City
Tel. No.: (632) 8-988-1000/8-988-7000
mail@themedicalcity.com

ANNEX 1.0
Documents Reviewed and Approved

Number	Document Name
1	Work Stress and Work Resilience Among Nurses Working in Extended Hours During COVID-19 Pandemic at Tertiary Hospitals in Metropolitan Manila, Philippines
	Version 3 August 2022

*** Nothing Follows ***

Ortigas Avenue, Pasig City
Tel. No.: (632) 8-988-1000/8-988-7000
mail@themedicalcity.com

CURRICULUM VITAE

Gian Rei A. Mangcucang, DipIH, EMT-B, RN

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EDUCATION

University of the Philippines Open University, Laguna, Philippines
Faculty of Management and Development Studies Expected December 2023

- Master of International Health

University of the Philippines Open University, Laguna, Philippines
Faculty of Management and Development Studies September 2016

- Diploma in International Health

City University of Marikina, Marikina City, Philippines
College of Nursing April 2012

- Bachelor of Science in Nursing

PROFESSIONAL EXPERIENCE

ASEAN Biodiaspora Virtual Center (ABVC) Manila, Philippines
Senior Health Program Officer March 2022 – Present

- Engaged with governance body and collaborate with Bluedot to prioritize regional analytic and innovation requirements for development into the ASEAN Biodiaspora tool.
- Worked with Bluedot, ASEAN Secretariat, and ASEAN Member States (AMS) to identify senior focal points for inclusion into project governance body.
- Monitored technology needs across the region for document information and analytic gaps within the ASEAN Region.
- Monitored project timelines, risks, and deliverables in the collaboration with other international team members.
- Managed and documented resources required and used in the ABVC operations.
- Served as the technical representative of the Biodiaspora project management team on external liaison and reporting in absence of the infectious Disease Office (IDO) Division Head and ABVC Program Manager.

Department of Health Center for Health Development IVB Quezon City, Philippines
Provincial DOH Office Marinduque Marinduque, Philippines
Nurse II – Nurse Deployment Program July 2019 – December 2021

- Assigned in Santa Cruz, Marinduque Rural Health Unit I/Municipal Health Office (MHO).
- Conducted regular visits to priority households with health issues and provided health education and appropriate interventions on identified health concerns of families/households.

- Prepared health status reports of families/households visited and assisted in the conduct implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of health programs.
- Conducted health education and training for health promotion and disease prevention among communities of Santa Cruz, Marinduque, Philippines.
- Coordinated with public health associates to ensure timely data collection and reporting.
- Assisted in the conduct of disease surveillance, monitored adverse effects of vaccines.
- Participated in data gathering and response during emergencies and disasters.
- Advocated for health need of the people in the island of Mongpong, Santa Cruz, Marinduque.
- Assisted to medical missions and free circumcision initiated by the office of the mayor of Santa Cruz, Marinduque.
- Actively participated in mobilization of COVID-19 vaccines in Santa Cruz, Marinduque.
- Initiated the use of social media and website to spread health awareness, increase health-seeking behavior, announcements related to the services offered by the MHO.

Marinduque Provincial Hospital

Marinduque, Philippines

Nurse II – Emergency Nurse

April 1-30, 2022

- Volunteered to augment staffing at the Marinduque Provincial Hospital during the first surge of COVID-19 in the Province of Marinduque, Philippines through the recommendation and coordination of Provincial DOH Office of Marinduque.
- Assisted and collaborated with ER physicians in treating patients at the emergency room.
- Monitored and carried out doctor’s orders for patients at the emergency room.
- Endorsed all admitted patients to ward staff nurses.

Commission on Population and Development Region IVA Mandaluyong City, Philippines
Batangas Provincial Health Office Batangas City, Philippines

Population Representative for Batangas Province

October 2018 – June 2019

- Conducted for regular visits of rural health units and collected accomplishments for unmet need and served clients for modern family planning methods.
- Motivated local government units (LGUs) to increase acceptance of modern family planning methods.
- Conducted trainings for health workers in LGUs.
- Assisted in implementation of Responsible Parenthood-Family Planning in LGUs.

St. Luke’s Medical Center Global City

Taguig City, Philippines

Emergency Care Services

Staff Nurse

October 2017 – August 2018

- Collaborated with physicians, other nurses and healthcare professionals.
- Provided care and monitors health conditions.
- Planned long-term care needs and administers medicine.
- Performed minor medical procedures.
- Advised and educated patients and their families on illness, medications, care and continued care after a hospital stay.

Marikina City Disaster Risk Reduction Management Office Marikina City, Philippines
Marikina City Rescue 161
Nurse I/EMT February 2014 – September 2017

- Responded to emergency calls to provide efficient and immediate care to the critically ill and injured patients.
- Transported patient to a medical facility when necessary.
- Acted independently in decision-making for treatment and transport of patients to medical facility.
- Acted as an Incident Commander during a disaster as the need arises.
- Performed triaging during a mass casualty incident for prioritization of treatment of patients.
- Performed rescue operations during calamities and disasters such as flash floods, earthquake, and high angle evacuation.
- Conducted trainings such as Basic Life Support, Basic Water Safety, Basic Disaster Risk Reduction and Management Training, and Disaster Response Capability and Rescue Operations Training to communities and other government agencies.
- Revised and updated the response sheet used by the ambulance teams of Rescue 161.

TRAINING AND SPECIALIZATION

Coursera – Johns Hopkins University Specialization in Epidemiology in Public Health Practice	2020
Life Support Training International Emergency Medical Technician – Basic	2015

AWARDS AND HONOR

Resolution 234 S. 2020 Commending Mr. Gian Rei Mangcucang, RN, NDP-Nurse II of Rural Health Unit I for Initiating a Donate a Blood Pressure (BP) Apparatus for the Benefit of Baranga Health Workers in Santa Cruz, Marinduque – Municipal Government of Santa Cruz, Marinduque, Philippines	2020
Academic Excellence in Care of Clients with Maladaptive Patterns of Behavior College of Nursing – City University of Marikina	2012
3 rd Place Intel Philippine Science Fair Regional Level “ <i>Pterygoplichthys pardalis</i> skin as an alternative for leather.”	2006

WORK IN PROGRESS

- Work Stress and Resilience Among Nurses Working in Extended Hours During COVID-19 Pandemic at Tertiary Hospitals in Metropolitan Manila, Philippines. Ethics approval, data collection, and analysis in progress.

VOLUNTEER WORK

Non-medical volunteer for Bayanihan E-Konsulta 2022

Free medical teleconsultation initiated by former Vice President Leni Robredo and implemented by Angat Pinas, Inc., Quezon City, Philippines

Volunteer to various medical missions 2015-2019

Initiated by Technical Rescue in Aid Group in Exigency, Corp., San Mateo, Rizal, Philippines